

Validation of the typology and classification system in Bulgaria for assessment the ecological status of surface water bodies of categories “river”, “lake” and “transitional waters”

Final Report

Annex 2

Methods for the analysis of BQEs, reference conditions and the ecological status classification system in the target types of surface waters

PHYTOPLANKTON

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Abbreviations

AGI	Algal Class index (= Catalan index)
AWB	Artificial water body
BQE	Biological quality elements
BV	Total biovolume
Chl-a	Chlorophyll-a
CIS	Common Implementation Strategy
EQR	Ecological quality ratio
EU	European Union
HMWB	Heavily modified water body
IC	Intercalibration
LOD	Limit of detection
MPI	Multimetric Phytoplankton Index
nEQR	Normalised ecological quality ratio
SD	Secchi depth
VGI	Catalan Index

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1 Introduction

Phytoplankton is one of the biological quality elements (BQE) required for the classification of ecological status and ecological potential of surface water bodies under the Water Framework Directive (WFD). It is relevant for lakes and reservoirs as well as for very large rivers.

Up to now, national classification methods have been developed for phytoplankton in the river Danube (= national river type R6, intercalibration [IC] type R-L2) (Mischke *et al.* 2016) and for lowland lakes belonging to the national lake type L5 (IC type L-EC1) (Borics *et al.* 2016; Borics *et al.* 2018). For other natural or heavily modified lakes, but also for artificial lakes and heavily modified rivers, which changed their category from ‘river’ to ‘lake’, a national method has been developed, which underwent no evaluation according to the requirements developed during the intercalibration phase and defined in the CIS Guidance No. 6, 14 and 30 (EU Commission 2002; 2011; 2015).

Activity 6.3 of the ToR requires the development/validation of the classification system for the assessment of the ecological status of river and lake types that have not yet been included in the intercalibration. This task includes:

- 1) An evaluation of existing classification methods and types to be considered;
- 2) An evaluation of available data on phytoplankton and relevant pressures;
- 3) Calculations of pressure-response relationships;
- 4) A definition of reference conditions and reference values for the relevant metrics;
- 5) Setting of class boundaries

Activity 6.4 of the ToR requires the development/validation of the classification system for the assessment of the ecological potential of river and lake types that have not yet been included in the intercalibration. This task includes:

- 1) The implementation of the approach adopted by the WG ECOSTAT and the water directors (integrated requirements of both CIS WFD approach and Prague approach of “mitigating measures”);
- 2) Considering the results of the process of defining/intercalibration of GEP in the WG ECOSTAT, sub-group GEP¹;
- 3) Considering the national approach for defining of GEP adopted in development of the 2nd RBMPs in Bulgaria;
- 4) Considering the Guidance of defining of GEP, developed in the project of Intercalibration of methods for analysis of BQEs for international types of surface waters in which Bulgaria participates;

As stated in the Document “Concept for determination of Good Ecological Potential in Bulgaria” the EP is of little relevance for phytoplankton. Although phytoplankton shall be part of the monitoring in HMWB (lakes/reservoirs, transitional R16), the ecological potential differs from the ecological status in the closest comparable category only where physical alterations do not allow reaching the environmental objectives (GES) and measures must be taken to reach at least GEP. As outlined in

¹ Strictly speaking, there is no intercalibration of GEP but an intercomparison of MEP and GEP among EU MS

Annex 1 of the Final Report (General document on defining the ecological potential in HMWB), the BQE phytoplankton of lakes is not significantly affected by physical alterations. The only exception (lake type L10) is discussed separately.

2 Revised typology

During the analysis of the data, it turned out that some of the reservoirs were probably incorrectly (or preliminarily?) assigned to the lake types as defined by Cheshmedjiev *et al.* (2010). In addition, some of the reservoir types (L11-L17) seem not clearly separated from each other based on the type description provided in the typology paper of Cheshmedjiev *et al.* (*op.cit.*). Finally, during discussions within the expert team and based on Annex 2 of the IV BMR, it became increasingly clear that trophic reference states should be taken into account in the definition of reservoir types. Therefore, we suggest to slightly revise the existing reservoir typology (only L11–L17) as follows (Table 1).

Table 1. Revised typology of reservoir types L11–L17 in the ecoregion (ER) 12 and 7 based on altitude and surface area. The numbers give the ranges of altitude and surface area within each type, n gives the number of reservoirs per type. The second column gives the new codes after Marinov *et al.* (2021b).

Code	Code	Type Description	ER	Altitude		Surface area		
old	new		n	min	max	min	max	
L11a	RL11a	Large (>10 km ²) mid-altitude (200-800 m asl) reservoirs in ER 12	2	12	256	814	9.6	27.6
L11b	RL11b	Large (>10 km ²) mid-altitude (200-400 m asl) reservoirs in ER 7	5	7	218	381	11.4	31.1
L11c	RL11c	Large (>10 km ²) high-altitude (>1,000 m asl) reservoirs in ER 7	1	7	1199		19.6	
L12	RL12	Small to medium-sized (<10 km ²) mid-altitude (200-800 m asl) reservoirs in ER12	16	12	205	695	0.5	5.4
L13	RL13	Small to medium-sized (<10 km ²) mid-altitude (200-800 m asl) reservoirs in ER 7	31	7	212	810	0.3	7.2
L14	RL14	Large (>5 km ²) lowland (<200 m asl) reservoirs in ER 12	5	12	59	189	5.1	18.4
L15	RL15	Large (>5 km ²) lowland (<200 m asl) reservoirs in ER 7	4	7	102	134	5.5	18.3
L16	RL16	Small to medium-sized (<5 km ²) lowland (<200 m asl) reservoirs in ER12	15	12	39	175	0.4	2.5
L17	RL17	Small to medium-sized (<5 km ²) lowland (<200 m asl) reservoirs in ER7	11	7	112	200	0.4	2.1

3 Available data on phytoplankton and pressures

Current analyses utilized data from different sources that varied in robustness, homogeneity and compatibility.

Three data sets were used in the analysis:

1. Data from the sampling campaign 2020
2. Data from the national monitoring of previous years
3. Data from IC project 2014–2016 (Borics *et al.* 2016)

3.1 Monitoring sites

The consolidated data set includes data from 126 monitoring sites belonging to 105 SWB (with up to 4 sites per SWB). The sites represent 17 lake types and 1 transitional river type (R16). The only national lake type not included is L5 with Lake Srebarna as the only representative. This lake type was successfully intercalibrated in 2017 (Borics *et al.* 2018).

The data annex in chapter 13 provides a complete list of all sites included in the analysis. In addition to the type of the surface water at the monitoring site, the table in the Annex also includes the SWB type. As the SWB in BG are defined rather broadly in some cases, they include different rivers and sometimes also small lakes. The altitude data were provided by the expert team working in the WB sister project on Hydromorphology (Cherrier 2021).

The following tables show the number of monitoring sites per type (and subtypes for L11) and category (Table 2), altitude class (Table 3), and surface area class (Table 4).

Table 2. Number of monitoring sites available per type and category.

Type	Artificial (AWB)	Heavily modified (HMWB)	Natural
L01		1	4
L02		5	
L03		6	1
L04	1	2	1
L05a			2
L06		1	2
L07		2	4
L08		3	3
L09	1	10	
L10		4	
L11a		2	
L11b		5	
L11c		3	
L12	2	10	
L13		16	
L14		7	
L15	1	2	
L16	2	11	
L17	1	3	
R16		1	8
sum	7	94	25

Table 3. Number of monitoring sites available per type and altitude class (in m above sea level).

Type	<200	200-500	500-800	800-1800	>1800
L01					5
L02		3	2		
L03				6	1
L04		2	1	1	
L05a	2				
L06	2		1		
L07	6				
L08	6				
L09	11				
L10	4				
L11a		1		1	
L11b		5			
L11c				3	
L12		11	1		
L13		11	4	1	
L14	7				
L15	3				
L16	12				
L17	4				
R16	9				
sum	66	33	9	12	6

Table 4. Number of monitoring sites available per lake type and surface area class. R16 not included as not applicable.

Type	<0.5 km ²	0.5-1 km ²	1-10 km ²	10-100 km ²	no data
L01		1			4
L02		2	3		
L03	1		5	1	
L04		2	1		1
L05a	2				
L06					3
L07			4	2	
L08	2		1	3	
L09	2		5	4	
L10			4		
L11a			1	1	
L11b				5	
L11c				3	
L12	1	5	6		
L13	5	1	10		
L14			3	4	
L15			2	1	
L16	1	5	6		
L17	1	1	2		
sum	15	17	53	24	17

3.2 Biological data

The biological data included partly raw data such as species lists, partly aggregated data and calculated metrics. The existing national methods for lakes in Bulgaria include the following metrics (Belkinova *et al.* 2013; MoEW 2020):

- Catalan Index (VGI)
- Total biovolume (BV, in $\text{mm}^3 \text{L}^{-1}$)
- Chlorophyll-a concentration (Chl-a, in $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)
- Relative proportion of Cyanobacteria (in %, calculated from BV)
- Blooms of toxic cyanobacteria (yes/no)
- Degree of blooms (classes zero, I, II and III)

Secchi depth (SD, in m) is a physico-chemical parameter but currently also used in the biological classification method. For the Lake Srebarna, a different index from Hungary (HLPI) was applied and successfully intercalibrated (Borics *et al.* 2018). It is a multimetric index, which includes chlorophyll-a and a composition metric (the so-called Q-index) as normalised EQR (see below in chapter 8). The Q-index is based on functional groups after (Padisák *et al.* 2006); Reynolds *et al.* (2002). In addition to these metrics, the major groups (algal classes) were calculated.

In addition to these data, taxa richness and Menhinick's index of diversity was calculated for the transitional waters belonging to L9, L10 and R16 – for explanation see below.

All three datasets mentioned above include data on these metrics, which were combined to a consolidated biological dataset. This data list includes also general data on sampling date, geographical coordinates, category (heavily modified water body HMWB, artificial water body AWB), lake type *etc.*

The sampling and analytical methods in the three datasets is the same and the analyses were carried out mostly by the same person. This guarantees a high degree of comparability of data from different years.

3.3 General physico-chemical data

In addition to the biological data, physico-chemical data is available from most sampling dates or from sampling dates close to the date of biological sampling. In the selection of older data the following rationale was applied:

Generally, no data with single sampling dates was used, as phytoplankton as well as physico-chemical parameters can significantly vary in concentration and abundance, respectively, within short time. Where sufficient data were available, only data with at least 3 sampling dates was used and aggregated as annual (arithmetic) mean. This approach led to a reduction of older data. The final dataset included mainly data from the monitoring years 2018 and 2019 (where most lakes were sampled at four sampling dates), while data from previous years (2016/2017) was partly excluded.

The following physico-chemical parameters were considered:

- General parameters: water temperature, electric conductivity, oxygen concentration and saturation, salinity, pH
- Nutrients: total phosphorus, total nitrogen, ammonium (as N), nitrate (as N), nitrite (as N), orthophosphate (as soluble reactive phosphorus SRP)
- Biological oxygen demand BOD₅

The final consolidated dataset with biological and physico-chemical data included:

- 328 samples with phytoplankton species data + physico-chemical data
- 611 samples with total biovolume or chlorophyll-a data + physico-chemical data
- 187 site-years with phytoplankton and/or physico-chemical data from at least three or four sampling dates; within this dataset: 153 site-years with both chlorophyll-a (or total biovolume) and total phosphorus concentration

Where physico-chemical concentrations were below the limit of detection (LOD), they were set at the LOD for further analyses. This procedure seemed more reasonable than setting them at 0. An alternative approach, *viz.* setting values below LOD at the half of the LOD, did not change the outcome significantly.

4 Descriptive analyses and similarity analyses

4.1 General physico-chemical parameters

A preliminary analysis carried out earlier by the phytobenthos experts show significant differences between lake types in terms of altitude and surface area (Figure 1). The higher altitude of lakes belonging to lake type L1, L3 and L11c is expected to correspond with a short duration of the vegetation period and lower water temperature.

Figure 1. Variation of altitude and surface area by types. Numbers at the top line indicate the number of monitoring sites used in the analysis.

A correlation analysis of the general physico-chemical parameters was carried out with complete datasets. Since BOD₅ was not available from several sites, a first analysis was carried out without this parameter. It showed that all parameters were significantly correlated with each other except PO₄-P vs NO₃-N (Table 5). When BOD₅ was included, also BOD₅ significantly correlated with all other parameter, except NO₃-N and NO₂-N. The lack of a significant correlation between PO₄-P and NO₃-N was surprising at the first moment, but can be explained by concentrations of orthophosphate-P often being below LOD resulted in several identical values.

Table 5. Spearman correlation coefficients for selected biological metrics based on phytoplankton. Database: all data 2008–2020 (only complete datasets), *single sampling dates*. lower left section = correlation coefficients, upper right section = significance level.

Parameter	SD	TN	NH ₄ -N	NO ₂ -N	NO ₃ -N	PO ₄ -P	TP
SD	–	<0.001	<0.001	0.019	0.005	<0.001	<0.001
TN	–0.22	–	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
NH₄-N	–0.21	0.61	–	<0.001	0.002	<0.001	<0.001
NO₂-N	–0.10	0.39	0.25	–	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
NO₃-N	–0.12	0.43	0.16	0.21	–	0.224	0.005
PO₄-P	–0.15	0.69	0.60	0.35	0.05	–	<0.001
TP	–0.26	0.71	0.64	0.37	0.12	0.89	–

The following boxplots illustrate the variability of selected parameters in different lake types and the river type R16 (Figure 2 to Figure 5).

Figure 2. Boxplots of Secchi depth (left) and BOD₅ (right) per lake type (and transitional river R16). Numbers at the top line indicate the number of samples per type.

Figure 3. Boxplots of total phosphorus (left) and orthophosphate-P (right) per lake type (and transitional river R16). Numbers at the top line indicate the number of samples per type.

Figure 4. Boxplots of nitrite-N (left) and nitrate-N (right) per lake type (and transitional river R16). Numbers at the top line indicate the number of samples per type.

Figure 5. Boxplots of total nitrogen (left) and ammonium-N (right) per lake type (and transitional river R16). Numbers at the top line indicate the number of samples per type.

4.2 Biological communities

Similarities among the biological communities from different monitoring sites were analysed using non-metric multi-dimensional scaling (nMDS) using the R package *Vegan* (Oksanen *et al.* 2020) of R version 4.1.2 (R Core Team 2021). The nMDS technique ranks samples on the basis of the similarity (Bray-Curtis distances) and produces a two-dimensional plot of the sample distribution, with short distances indicating high similarity between sites. A numerical measure of the fit between the similarities in the two-dimensional plot and the original data is given as the stress index. Using nMDS allowed us to illustrate the data structure, and thus provide graphical support for our interpretation of the interrelations and possible effects of different factors.

The nMDS in Figure 6 is based on all phytoplankton single sample analyses at species/ genus level. Grouping factor is the sampling season. The plot reveals a seasonal impact, although spring samples are underrepresented and no samples from March or April are available. Nevertheless, one can see clear seasonal differences that underline the importance of more than one or two sampling occasions during a year.

The same nMDS plot with lake type as grouping factor is shown in Figure 7. The overlap of the different lake types does not reveal clear differences. Two groups of types, however, separate slightly from other types in terms of the taxonomic composition of the phytoplankton: the high-alpine and mountain lakes (L01, L03) and the transitional lakes L09 and L10 as well as the transitional river type R16. When these five types are removed from the analysis, the remaining types split up again, revealing for instance differences between L06/L07/L08 versus L11/L13 (Figure 8).

Figure 6. nMDS plot on phytoplankton raw data (species, single sampling dates) in BG lakes (+ transitional type R16), grouped by sampling season. Database: sampling campaigns 2020.

Figure 7. nMDS plot on phytoplankton raw data (species, single sampling dates) in BG lakes (+ transitional type R16), grouped by type. Database: sampling campaigns 2020.

Figure 8. nMDS plot on phytoplankton raw data (species, single sampling dates) in BG lakes, grouped by type (without L01, L03, L09, L10 and transitional river type R16). Database: sampling campaigns 2020.

Comparable analyses were carried out on the basis of annual means. Like for the single dates, a strong overlap was observed, but some lake differ significantly in terms of the taxonomic composition of the phytoplankton communities, in Figure 9 again the high-alpine lake type L01, but also the riparian lakes and marshes in ER 12-2, Arkutino and Veliov vir.

Another analysis focused on the functional groups as defined by Reynolds *et al.* (2002) (Figure 10) and revealed general differences between lake types, which partly support the current national typology. Table 6 gives selected examples. There is, however, no general pattern, which fully separates lake types based on the functional groups, maybe because of the seasonal variability in the occurrence and dominance of functional groups, which is not included in the annual-average-based analysis in Figure 10.

Table 6. Examples of occurrence of selected functional groups after Reynolds *et al.* (2002) in BG lake types and lakes.

Funct. group	Preferred habitat acc. to Reynolds	Tolerances	Sensitivities	Typically found in ...
D	Shallow, enriched turbid waters, including rivers	Flushing	Nutrient depletion	dam Mandra – iztok (L07) Lake Shabla (L07) Chirpan Reservoir (L17) Fandakliyska River estuary (R16)
E	Usually small, oligotrophic base poor lakes or heterotrophic ponds	Low nutrients	CO ₂ depletion	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir (L14) Dolna Dikanya Reservoir (L13) Chernoto Lake (L01)
F	Clear epilimnia	low nutrients, high turbidity	?CO ₂ deficiency	Malko Sharkovo Reservoir (L13) Al. Stamboliyski Reservoir (L14) Zhrebchevo Reservoir (L11b)
L₀	Summer epilimnia in mesotrophic lakes	Segregated nutrients	Prolonged or deep mixing	Piasachnik Reservoir (L11b) Bezbog Lake (L01) Golyam Beglik Reservoir (L03) Kremensko ezero (L01)
S1	Turbid mixed layers	Highly light deficient	Flushing	Rozov Kladenets Reservoir (L15) General Nikolaevo Res. (L17) Burgas Lake – east (L08) Protected Area “Zlato pole” (L06) Lakes of type L07

Figure 9. nMDS plot on the relative proportions of phytoplankton major groups (calculated from annual means) in BG lakes (+ transitional type R16), grouped by type. Database: sampling campaigns 2020.

Figure 10. nMDS plot on the relative proportions of phytoplankton functional groups according to (Reynolds *et al.* 2002), calculated from annual means, in BG lakes (+ transitional type R16), grouped by type. Database: sampling campaigns 2020.

4.3 Correlation among biological metrics

As mentioned above, several biological metrics are currently in use for the classification of lakes based on phytoplankton. Total biovolume (BV) and chlorophyll-a (chl) can be considered of proxy of the phytoplankton biomass and, in consequence, reflect primary productivity. They are significantly correlated (Figure 11 left, Figure 12 left), which confirms the accuracy of the chemical and biological analyses. The median relative proportion of chl in BV over all samples ($n=735$) is 0.44% (20th and 80th percentiles are 0.20 and 1.01%). Both algal metric are also significantly correlated with Secchi depth, underlining the secondary effect of increased phytoplankton density and biomass on the light conditions in standing waters (Figure 11 right, Figure 12 right).

The correlation between BV and chl on the one hand and calculated phytoplankton indices on the other hand is shown in Table 7. Three indices are included: the Catalan index (Algae Group Index, AGI or VGI), the Hungarian lake phytoplankton index (HLPI) and the Q-index which is based on functional groups (Padisák *et al.* 2006; Reynolds *et al.* 2002) and is part of the HLPI. All of them are significantly correlated with each other when based on single samples (Table 7), while all combinations but BV vs Q when based on annual averages (Table 8, Figure 13).

Figure 11. Correlation between total biovolume and chlorophyll-a concentration (left, $n=735$) and Secchi depth (right, $n=701$) at *single sampling dates*. Database: all data 2008–2020.

Figure 12. Correlation between total biovolume and chlorophyll-a concentration (left, $n=180$) and Secchi depth (right, $n=174$) based on *annual means*. Database: all data 2008–2020.

Table 7. Spearman correlation coefficients for selected biological metrics based on phytoplankton. Database: data from 2020 (no complete dataset on these metrics from previous years), *single sampling dates*. lower left section = correlation coefficients, upper right section = significance level.

	AGI	Q	BV	Chl
AGI	–	<0.001	<0.001	0.002
Q	–0.32	–	0.006	0.002
BV	0.26	–0.15	–	<0.001
Chl	0.17	–0.17	0.46	–

AGI = Algae Group Index, Q = phytoplankton Q index based on functional groups, BV = total biovolume, chl = chlorophyll-a concentration

Table 8. Spearman correlation coefficients for selected biological metrics based on phytoplankton. Database: data from 2020 (no complete dataset on these metrics from previous years), *annual means*. lower left section = correlation coefficients, upper right section = significance level.

	AGI	Q	BV	Chl
AGI	–	0.005	0.002	0.003
Q	–0.30	–	0.252	0.020
BV	0.33	–0.12	–	<0.001
Chl	0.32	–0.25	0.68	–

Abbreviations see Table 7

Figure 13. Correlation plot (Spearman correlation coefficient) with various phytoplankton metrics (abbreviations see Table 7) as annual means. Database: data from 2020 (no complete dataset on these metrics from previous years).

5 Pressure – response relationships

During the intercalibration exercise and in numerous projects on the evaluation of anthropogenic pressures on phytoplankton, total phosphorus (TP) has turned out as main and most expository pressure indicator (Philipps *et al.* 2017; Solheim *et al.* 2008; Wolfram *et al.* 2009). At high TP levels, other elements can limit primary productivity as well and, hence, be useful as additional pressure indicator, *e.g.*, total nitrogen (TN) or silicate. This can especially be the case in small ponds or in shallow lakes with extensive littoral zones, where denitrification plays a significant role; also co-limitation – optionally temporally fluctuating – can occur in some lakes (Downing & McCauley 1992; Kolzau *et al.* 2014; Maberly *et al.* 2020).

Concerning the link between driving forces and pressure in the catchment area, we refer to the WB sister project on diffuse pollution, where these correlations were extensively studied (Wolfram 2021a; b).

The most direct impact of nutrients on phytoplankton is the potential to increase the phytoplankton biomass. Both TP and TN are significantly correlated with chlorophyll-a in an analysis including alle BG lake and reservoir types (Figure 14, Table 9, Table 10). A multiple regression model (Table 11)

revealed that both nutrients have a significant impact on the phytoplankton biomass. The model with both nutrients as independent variables had a significantly higher explanation power than the linear models with single variables (Table 12).

Figure 14. Correlation between total phosphorus (left) and total nitrogen (right), respectively, and chlorophyll-a concentration (n=143). Database: *annual means 2020*.

Table 9. Linear regression total phosphorus *versus* chlorophyll-a.

Linear regression model: Chlorophyll-a ~ Total phosphorus

Call:

```
lm(formula = log10(Chl) ~ log10(TP))
```

TP and Chl in µg/L

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.13966	-0.28944	0.03295	0.29731	1.02227

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.18311	0.11231	-1.63	0.105
log10(x1c)	0.79821	0.06116	13.05	<2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.4249 on 150 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.5318, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5287

F-statistic: 170.4 on 1 and 150 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Table 10. Linear regression total nitrogen *versus* chlorophyll-a.

Linear regression model: Chlorophyll-a ~ Total nitrogen					
Call: lm(formula = log10(Chl) ~ log10(TN)) Chl in µg/L, TN in mg/L					
Residuals:					
Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max	
-1.33354	-0.38234	0.07717	0.39166	1.05129	
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)	
(Intercept)	1.31279	0.04221	31.100	< 2e-16	***
log10(x1c)	0.96569	0.10740	8.992	1.46e-15	***
--- Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1					
Residual standard error: 0.4918 on 141 degrees of freedom					
Multiple R-squared: 0.3644, Adjusted R-squared: 0.3599					
F-statistic: 80.85 on 1 and 141 DF, p-value: 1.457e-15					

Table 11. Multiple linear regression model: total phosphorus and total nitrogen *versus* chlorophyll-a.

Multiple linear regression model: Chlorophyll-a ~ Total phosphorus + Total nitrogen					
Call: lm(formula = log10(Chl) ~ log10(TN) + log10(TP)) TP and Chl in µg/L, TN in mg/L					
Residuals:					
Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max	
-1.06288	-0.26855	0.01695	0.28718	0.91840	
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)	
(Intercept)	0.12542	0.15946	0.787	0.433	
log10(x1)	0.64185	0.08402	7.639	3.13e-12	***
log10(x2)	0.30292	0.12541	2.416	0.017	*
--- Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1					
Residual standard error: 0.4147 on 140 degrees of freedom					
Multiple R-squared: 0.5514, Adjusted R-squared: 0.545					
F-statistic: 86.04 on 2 and 140 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16					

Table 12. ANOVA for comparison of models.

Analysis of Variance Table						
Model 1: log10(y1) ~ log10(x1) + log10(x2)						
Model 2: log10(y1) ~ log10(x1)						
	Res.Df	RSS	Df	Sum of Sq	F	Pr(>F)
1	140	24.075				
2	141	25.078	-1	-1.0033	5.8347	0.017 *

Like for the nutrient vs biomass regressions, the relationships between TP and the two metrics AGI and Q index were analysed. Transitional water bodies from L09, L10 and R16 were excluded as the Q index was developed for freshwater taxa only. Both AGI and Q index turned out to be significant ($p < 0.001$), which means that the anthropogenic impact on the nutrient status affects the biological metrics (Figure 15). This finding supports using at least one of them in the classification of

eutrophication in standing waters. However, the variance explained is much lower than for chlorophyll-a. Total phosphorus explains only 22% and 17% of the variance of AGI and Q index, respectively (cf Figure 15). The poor performance of AGI and Q index is not surprising. The Catalan index is based on major taxa which comprise species of highly different ecological preferences (Marchetto *et al.* 2009). It should thus be applied with caution in the classification of anthropogenic pressures (Belkinova *et al.* 2014). The Q index, on the other hand, has been identified as a reliable instrument to assess ecological status (Padisák *et al.* 2006) and successfully tested at shallow tropical, deep subtropical and deep Mediterranean reservoirs (Becker *et al.* 2009; Crossetti & Bicudo 2008). Belkinova *et al.* (2014) stress its advantage over the other indices as it reflects general anthropogenic pressure.

Table 13. Linear regression total phosphorus *versus* the Q index (excluding types L09, L10 and R16).

Linear regression model: Q index ~ Total phosphorus					
Call:					
lm(formula = Q ~ log10(TP))					
TP in µg/L					
Residuals:					
Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max	
-3.5010	-0.7513	0.1646	1.0488	2.1488	
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)	
(Intercept)	7.1750	0.4274	16.788	< 2e-16	***
log10(x1c)	-0.9166	0.2625	-3.492	0.000925	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1					
Residual standard error: 1.333 on 58 degrees of freedom					
Multiple R-squared: 0.1737, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1595					
F-statistic: 12.19 on 1 and 58 DF, p-value: 0.0009246					

Figure 15. Correlation total phosphorus *versus* the Catalan-Index (AGI, left) and the Q index on functional groups (right). Database: *annual means 2018–2020*, excluding transitional water bodies of types L09, L10 and R16.

Concluding, although using the Q index or the AGI have some explanatory power, their value in identifying nutrient impact alone is clearly smaller than that of chlorophyll-a. For the classification of the ecological status of BG lakes and reservoirs in general it can be sensitive since it covers also other pressures on the phytoplankton such as hydrological impacts. Overall, it is justified to combine the strengths of the metrics chlorophyll-a and Q index (which performs slightly better than AGI) and use the HLPI for phytoplankton classification in Bulgaria.

As stated above, the Q index cannot be calculated for the transitional waters of type L09, L10 and R16, as it was developed for freshwater taxa. To integrate the parameters *taxonomic composition* and *abundance* in the classification (as required in Annex V of the WFD) we tested the use of various diversity metrics. They performed very similar. Therefore it was decided to use Menhinick's index as part of the MPI which was successfully tested and applied also during the IC exercise (Ponis *et al.* 2018). Menhinick's index is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Menhinick's index} = S / \text{square root}(n)$$

S ... taxa richness

n ... abundance

As shown in Figure 16 and Table 14, the correlation between TP and the Menhinick's index is significant and thus reflects trophic impacts. It shall be used in the transitional waters.

Figure 16. Correlation total phosphorus *versus* Menhinick's index (Database: *annual means 2018–2020*. Only transitional water bodies of types L09, L10 and R16.

Table 14. Linear regression total phosphorus *versus* Menhinick's index (only transitional water bodies of types L09, L10 and R16).

Linear regression model: Menhinick's index ~ Total phosphorus					
Call:					
lm(formula = Menhinick's index ~ log10(TP))					
TP in µg/L					
Residuals:					
Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max	
-0.019144	-0.003856	-0.001843	0.002821	0.018454	
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)	
(Intercept)	0.049570	0.011968	4.142	0.000997	***
log10(x1c)	-0.014503	0.005797	-2.502	0.025375	*

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1					
Residual standard error: 0.009573 on 14 degrees of freedom					
Multiple R-squared: 0.309, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2596					
F-statistic: 6.259 on 1 and 14 DF, p-value: 0.02537					

Two further metrics used in transitional waters are Hurlburt's index of diversity and bloom frequency. Together they are part of the multimetric index MPI after Ponis *et al.* (2018). The authors of the GIG on Mediterranean transitional waters demonstrated that Hurlburt's index correlate with dilution and can thus be used to indicate an additional pressure apart from eutrophication. For further explanation on MPI see below in chapter 9.

6 Trophic classes and nutrient thresholds in lakes and reservoirs

6.1 Paleolimnological evidence

Paleolimnological and historical data in Bulgarian are available from a couple of lakes, mainly from high-altitude lakes (*e.g.*, Stefanova *et al.* (2003)) and the Sofia basin (*e.g.*, Ognjanova-Rumenova *et al.* (2008)). Filipova-Marinova *et al.* (2013) investigated Varna Lake and found anthropogenic impacts on the lake dating back to the Late Eneolithic and Early Bronze Age. The algal species composition found in the sediment by the authors reflect a brackish water environment and relatively eutrophic waters during the Late Eneolithic, when the Black Sea level was low and soils around Varna Lake were suitable for cultivation.

The few paleoecological studies available demonstrate that enhanced trophic states occurred already in times before intensive anthropogenic impacts. The paleolimnological data prove evidence that a eutrophic state was natural and represented reference conditions in some lake types. However, the information on paleolimnology is not sufficient to precisely define the trophic reference conditions in Bulgarian lakes belonging to different lake types.

6.2 Trophic classes (Annex II of IV BMR)

As part of this project, the expert team proposed trophic groups for the Bulgarian lakes and reservoirs (Table 15). The trophic state of the three lake types L1 to L3 can be defined as ultra-oligotrophic and oligotrophic, respectively, with high confidence. This complies with comparable lakes in the Alps (Poikane *et al.* 2010; Wolfram *et al.* 2009) and Scandinavia (Phillips & Pitt 2016; Poikane *et al.* 2010) and can be used as additional information to define reference conditions.

Table 15. Trophic classes per lake type (new codes) based on phytoplankton as suggested in Annex 2 of the IV BMR (Marinov *et al.* 2021a) (modified). The boundary values for chlorophyll-a (chl-a) correspond to those given in OECD (1982), only the range for oligo-mesotrophic lakes is based in expert judgment.

Trophic status groups / subgroups		Type code	Type name	Chl-a, $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
oligo-trophic	Ultra-oligotrophic	L1	Glacial high-mountain lakes (Alpine Lakes)	<1.0
	Oligotrophic	L2	Mountain Lakes in ER 12	<2.5
		L3	Mountain Lakes in ER7	
mesotrophic	Oligo-mesotrophic	L4	Lowland & semi-mountain lakes and swamps in ER 12	(1.5–5.0)
		RL11	Large deep reservoirs	
		RL12	Medium-size and small semi-mountain reservoirs in the ER 12	
	Mesotrophic	RL13	Medium-size and small semi-mountain reservoirs in ER 7	2.5–8.0
		RL14	Large lowland reservoirs up to middle depth in ER 12	
eutrophic	Eutrophic	RL15	Large lowland reservoirs up to middle depth in ER 77	8.0–25.0
		L5	Riparian lakes and marshes in ER 12-1 ^{*)}	
		RL16	Small and medium size lowland reservoirs in ER 12	
	Hypertrophic	RL17	Small and medium size lowland reservoirs in ER 7	≥ 25.0
		L5a	Riparian marshes in ER 12-2	
		L6	Riparian wetlands in ER 7	
		TFL7	Black Sea coastal freshwater lakes	
		TOL8	Black Sea coastal oligohaline lakes	

*) For the intercalibrated lake type L5 in ER 12-1, a reference value for chlorophyll-a of $11.8 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ was determined.

6.3 Chlorophyll-a thresholds and lake type groups according to national ordinance H-4 MoEW (2020)

The current national ordinance (Table 16) gives chlorophyll-a thresholds for L1–L3 which are significantly higher than those given above for the trophic groups, possibly because the three types are grouped together with L11–L13. The H/G boundary for the types L11–L14 (Chl-a $4 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) complies with the range given above for oligo-mesotrophic and mesotrophic lakes (1.5–5.0 and 2.5–8.0 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively). The H/G boundary for all other lake types seems to be too strict as it also lies at $4 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and thus lower than the OECD range for eutrophic and hypertrophic lakes.

Table 16. Metrics and non-normalised EQR values for the BQE phytoplankton in different national lake types at the class boundaries High/Good (H/G), Good/Moderate (G/M), Moderate/Poor (M/P) and Poor/Bad (P/B) according to the national Ordinance H-4. Source: MoEW (2020).

National type	IC type	EQR, metric	H/G ^{*)}	G/M ^{*)}	M/P ^{*)}	P/B ^{*)}
L1, L2, L3, L11, L12, L13	–	EQR (VGI)	0.998	0.995	0.975	0.950
		VGI (Catalan Index)	0.9	2.0	10	20
		BV (mm ³ L ⁻¹)	1	5	8	10
		Chl-a (µg L ⁻¹)	4	10	15	50
		SD (m)	4	2	1.5	1
		% Cyanobacteria	4	15	20	50
		Blooms of toxic cyanobacteria	No	No	No/Yes	Yes
		Degree of blooms	–	(+)	I	II–III
L4, L6, L7, L8, L9, L10, L14, L15, L16, L17	–	EQR (VGI)	0.998	0.994	0.975	0.950
		VGI (Catalan Index)	1.0	2.5	10	20
		BV (mm ³ L ⁻¹)	1.5	7	15	25
		Chl-a (µg L ⁻¹)	4	10	20	50
		SD (m)	4	2	1	0.6
		% Cyanobacteria	4	15	20	50
		Blooms of toxic cyanobacteria	No	No/Yes	Yes	Yes
		Degree of blooms	–	I	II	III
L5a	–	EQR (VGI)	0.997	0.994	0.975	0.950
		VGI (Catalan Index)	1.2	2.5	10	20
		BV (mm ³ L ⁻¹)	5	10	20	40
		Chl-a (µg L ⁻¹)	17.5	35	70	140
		SD (m)	NA	NA	NA	NA
		% Cyanobacteria	4	15	20	50
		Blooms of toxic cyanobacteria	No	No/Yes	Yes	Yes
		Degree of blooms	0–II	II–III	II–III	III
L5	L-EC1	HLPI	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20

^{*)} A value situated exactly on a boundary belongs to the better status class

NA = not applicable

The EQR values given in the Ordinance of the MoEW as amended in 2020 comply from those given in the EU Decision from 2018 (Decision 2018/229/EU) after revision by Borics et al. (2018) for the lake type L5 (only Lake Srebarina).

6.4 Nutrient thresholds according to national ordinance H-4 MoEW (2020)

The following Table 17 summarises the class boundaries for the relevant nutrient concentrations (total phosphorus, total nitrogen, nitrate-N) in Bulgarian lakes given in the Ordinance No. H-4 from 2012, as amended (MoEW 2020).

Like for chlorophyll-a (Table 16), only two main groups are distinguished for nutrients: group 1 with L1–3 and L11–13, group 2 with the remaining types (except L5 / L5a). The G/M boundary for group 1

of lake types lies at $40 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, for group 2 at $75 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Hence, eutrophic conditions with $\text{TP} > 35 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Vollenweider & Kerekes 1982) would still be in good ecological status in all lake types.

Table 17. Values for total phosphorus (TP), total nitrogen (TN) and nitrate-N ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) related to the ecological status by types of surface waters.

Ecological status	TP, mg L^{-1}		TN, mg L^{-1}		$\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, mg L^{-1}	
	L1, L2, L3, L11, L12, L13	L4, L6, L7, L8, L14, L15, L16, L17	L1, L2, L3, L11, L12, L13	L4, L6, L7, L8, L14, L15, L16, L17	L1, L2, L3, L11, L12, L13	L4, L6, L7, L8, L14, L15, L16, L17
High	<0.0125	<0.025	<0.2	<0.7	<0.2	<0.8
Good	0.0125–0.04	0.025–0.075	0.2–0.8	0.7–2.5	0.2–0.5	0.8–2.0
Moderate	>0.04	>0.075	>0.8	>2.5	>0.5	>2.0

6.5 Evaluation of nutrient thresholds in the World Bank project on diffuse pollution

In the sister project of the WB, a thorough validation of existing thresholds was carried out (Wolfram 2021a). Different statistical, and comparisons with the literature (Phillips & Pitt 2016) and validation with traditional eutrophication models (Vollenweider & Kerekes 1982) were used to derive class boundaries for total phosphorus and total nitrogen.

For **total phosphorus**, the following conclusions were drawn (cited from Wolfram (2021a), not yet coordinated within the expert team of the project on typology and classification!):

- *The existing TP boundaries for the high-altitude lakes >2000 m asl (L1) seem to be far too high. Depending in their size and depth (which is not considered in the type description), they can be assumed to be ultraoligotrophic or oligotrophic. In remote Alpine lakes, dissolved P concentrations around $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ were found (e.g., Rofner et al. (2016)). Hence a HG boundary clearly around $5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and a GM boundary around $10\text{--}15 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ seems justified for natural and remote glacial lakes.*
- *A TP concentration of $12.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for the HG boundary of mountain lakes belonging to the BG national type L2 and L3 is justified if they are shallow (polymictic). $40 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for the GM boundary seems too high, as it already lies within the range of eutrophic conditions. Values between 20 and $35 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ seem more plausible.*
- *In the coastal lakes (L7–L10), the existing boundaries as defined in the Ordinance H-4 from 2012 as amended in 2020 appear plausible. However, a closer look and additional type characteristics apart from salinity is strongly recommended to get better insight into the factors determining the trophic state.*
- *For the deep and dimictic reservoirs belonging to lake type L11, oligotrophic conditions can be accepted as trophic state required for the maximum potential. Hence, a HG boundary of $12.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ may be too high. This seems even more to be the case for the GM boundary ($40 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), which should probably be closer to the meso/eutrophic trophic class boundary.*

- *Some of the L12 and L13 reservoirs may be better classified as oligotrophic, too, thus deserving a lower GM boundary to achieve the good ecological potential. However, this should be clarified with more data on reservoir depth, hydrological conditions and surrounding landcover.*
- *Reservoirs belonging to L14–L17 are considered as mesotrophic in the type description. The existing HG boundaries comply with this, while GM boundary seems again to be too high.*
- *For the remaining lake types, the picture is unclear, and the calculations do not justify recommending a change of existing boundaries. This does not necessarily mean they can be considered as “correct”, but more data is needed to draw conclusions with confidence.*

Concluding, at present several boundaries seem to be too high (= too relaxed), while no boundary seems to be too strict. Generally, the distance between HG and GM boundaries are very high, allowing a significant increase of eutrophication within the good status class (defined by TP) before the GM boundary is exceeded.

For **total nitrogen (TN)**, similar to TP, there is an obvious difference between the threshold values derived from different approaches, however, the proposed ranges also overlap in several cases. The comparison of existing boundaries in Bulgaria (Ordinance H-4 from 2012, as amended in 2020) with those developed in other EU Member States reveals that especially the GM boundary currently defined in the national Ordinance seems to be too high. Most boundaries for broad lake types defined in other EU Member States are below 2.5 mg L^{-1} .

Based on the data analyses, the following conclusions can be drawn (cited from Wolfram (2021a), not yet coordinated within the expert team of the project on typology and classification!):

- *The existing TN boundaries for L1 to L3 are reasonable. The data analysis does not justify a change of these values with sufficient confidence.*
- *The GM boundary of 2.5 mg L^{-1} for TN is higher than the values proposed for various types and by using different approaches. ... For the time being, maximum GM boundaries of 2 mg L^{-1} seem more reasonable than 2.5 mg/l as currently defined for several lake types.*
- *For the transitional lake types, uncertainties in the data evaluation are too high to recommend class boundaries for TN. Is it necessary to characterise and monitor these lake types more intensively in order to identify similarities and dissimilarities with transitional waters in other countries, which could help to define narrower ranges of likely boundary values than those derived from all transitional types in the EU.*

The following Figure 17 gives an insight into the variability of G/M boundaries for total phosphorus in different broad European lake types *sensu* Solheim *et al.* (2019).

Figure 17. Range of national good/moderate boundary TP values for broad lake types *sensu* Solheim *et al.* (2019) where method used was not expert judgement or from distribution in all water bodies (redrawn from data collated by Phillips & Pitt (2016)) Source: Phillips *et al.* (2018).

7 Reference values and the class boundaries for total phosphorus and total nitrogen

7.1 Lakes and reservoirs

The previous chapters aimed at illustrating the different approaches, concepts and databases used by various authors and experts to define reference conditions for BG lakes. In this chapter we summarise the outcome and propose type-specific reference values and class boundaries for total phosphorus. They are the result in thorough internal discussions and can be considered as best guess, based on extensive data analysis and finally evaluated by expert judgment.

L1 Glacial high-mountain lakes (Alpine Lakes)

Six SWB are assigned to lake type L1, all of them located above 2000 m asl (Table 18). Cheshmedjiev *et al.* (2010) describe these lakes as very small (<0.15 m²). The surface areas given in Table 18 probably refer to a hull around several small water bodies (“lake groups”) and not single lakes.

Under reference conditions, very low nutrient levels can be expected for L1. The TP class boundaries given in the national ordinance H-4 (MoEW 2020) seem too high compared with lakes in the altitude class 800-1800 m asl. In the lake typology report submitted with the IV Progress Report, L1 lakes were described as (ultra-) oligotrophic (Marinov *et al.* 2021a). This correspond to a mean TP concentration of 4 µg L⁻¹ in the fixed boundary system of the OECD trophic classification scheme (Vollenweider & Kerekes 1982).

Based on this, we propose a mean annual TP concentration of $3 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ as reference value, while 5 and $12 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ are suggested for the H/G and G/M boundaries, respectively (Table 19). The G/M boundary is based on findings that the phytoplankton community of ultra-oligotrophic lakes can significantly change when the concentrations are increased by a factor 2–3. The M/P and P/B boundaries are defined as twice as high as the boundaries of the better status in each case. For TN concentrations, the boundaries defined in Ordinance H-4 can be accepted. Reference value and the lower class boundaries are defined based on a factor 2 by expert judgment (Table 20).

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in L1 lakes are below $10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for TP (n=5 site-years, LOD within G status class!) and range from 0.12 to 0.66 mg L^{-1} for TN (n=5).

Table 18. Lakes belonging to type L1.

SWB code	SWB name	Category	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG1IS900L1002	Beli Iskar ISRWB1002	HMWB	2074	0.8	19
BG4ME700L1009	Lake group "Western Pirin"	natural	2363	3.9	–
BG4ST500L1004	Karagyol Kalin lake	HMWB	2474	2.0	10
BG4ST500L1010	Lake group "Eastern Pirin"	natural	2294	8.9	–
BG4ST600L1007	Lake group "Western Rila"	natural	2239	4.1	–
BG4ST600L1018	Lake group "Southern Rila"	natural	2235	4.3	–

Table 19. Reference values and class boundaries for TP ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to type L1. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), median other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Boundary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types		Proposal
			median other MS		
			type 11 highland siliceous	type 12 highland calc./mixed	
Reference					3
H/G	12.5	5			5
G/M	40	10–15	16	15	12
M/P					24
P/B					48

Table 20. Reference values and class boundaries for TN (mg L^{-1}) in lakes belonging to type L1. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), median other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Boundary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types		Proposal
			median other MS		
			type 11 highland siliceous	type 12 highland calc./mixed	
Reference					0.1
H/G	0.2	0.2			0.2
G/M	0.8	0.8	0.25	na	0.8
M/P					2.0
P/B					4.0

L2 Mountain Lakes in ER 12

Only four SWB are assigned to lake type L2, all of them are heavily modified (Table 21). The altitude of these four lakes varies between 336 and 610 m asl. Based on data on the volume of these reservoirs, a mean depth of 13–28 m can be calculated for three of the four SWB. They thus can be assumed to be stratified. Low nutrient concentrations, though slightly higher than L1, can be expected.

In the deliverable N1.3 part I of the WB sister project on diffuse pollution, a H/G of 12–13 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and a G/M boundary of 20–35 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ was considered as appropriate if the lakes were shallow (Wolfram 2021a). The data show, however, that this is not the case. Hence, lower boundaries seem more justified, more resembling oligotrophic conditions as also suggested lake typology report submitted with the IV Progress Report (Marinov *et al.* 2021a). In the fixed boundary system of the OECD trophic classification scheme a TP concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ was suggested (Vollenweider & Kerekes 1982). The mean values for the broad types 7 or 8 *sensu* Solheim *et al.* (2019) seem comparable to the BG lake type L2.

Therefore, we propose a mean annual TP concentration of 4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ as reference value and 8 and 16 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ as H/G and G/M boundaries, respectively (Table 22). For TN concentrations, the boundaries defined in Ordinance H-4 can be accepted. Reference value and the lower class boundaries are defined based on a factor 2 by expert judgment (Table 23).

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in L2 lakes range from below the LOD (10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) to 17 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for TP (n=7) and from 0.16 to 0.46 mg L^{-1} for TN (n=5).

Table 21. Lakes belonging to type L2.

SWB code	SWB name	Category	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG1IS200L1021	Bebresh ISRWB1021	HMWB	492	0.9	–
BG1IS600L1014	Ognyanovo ISRWB1014	HMWB	610	2.4	13
BG1YN600L1019	Yovkovtsi YNRWB1019	HMWB	336	6.3	15
BG1YN900L1014	Hristo Smirnenski YNRWB1014	HMWB	533	1.0	28

Table 22. Reference values and class boundaries for TP ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to type L2. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Boundary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types				Proposal
			most probably range		median other MS		
			shallow polymictic	type 8 mean depth <15 m, calc.	type 8 mean depth >15 m, calc.	type 7 mid-alt., siliceous	
Reference						4	
H/G	12.5	12.5	9–14	5–8		8	
G/M	40	<<40	22–27	11–15	16	30	
M/P						30	
P/B						60	

Table 23. Reference values and class boundaries for TN (mg L^{-1}) in lakes belonging to type L2. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Boundary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types				Proposal
			most probably range		median other MS		
			shallow polymictic	type 8 mean depth <15 m, calc.	type 8 mean depth >15 m, calc.	type 7 mid-alt., siliceous	
Reference							0.1
H/G	0.2	0.2	na	na	na	na	0.2
G/M	0.8	0.8	na	na	0.43	na	0.8
M/P							2.0
P/B							4.0

L3 Mountain Lakes in ER 7

Six SWB are assigned to lake type L3. In terms of altitude, they lie between L1 and L3 (range 1100–1906 m asl), suggesting oligotrophic conditions as suggested by Marinov *et al.* (2021a) in the lake typology report submitted with the IV Progress Report. The statement of Wolfram (2021a) in the final report of the Diffuse Pollution Project does not apply, since most (if not all) L3 lakes are deep stratified reservoirs (Table 24). Among the broad lake types *sensu* Solheim *et al.* (2019), type 7 is most comparable with BG type L3, since the low conductivity clearly reveals siliceous geology. Electric conductivity varies between 26 and 81 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ (n=6), slightly higher than L1 (8–27 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, n=5), but much lower than L2 (204–299 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, n=5). Comparability with the broad types 13–15 (Mediterranean, no altitude given but differing in geology and size) is doubtful. Cheshmedjiev *et al.* (2010) describe the geology of L3 lakes vaguely as “organic (peat), mixed, siliceous, calcareous”.

Based on these findings and taking into account the values suggested for L1 and L2, we propose a mean annual TP concentration of 4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ as reference value and 8 and 16 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ as H/G and G/M boundaries, respectively (Table 25). For TN concentrations, the boundaries defined in Ordinance H-4 can be accepted. Reference value and the lower class boundaries are defined based on a factor 2 by expert judgment (Table 26).

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in L3 lakes range from below the LOD (10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) to 30 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for TP (n=8) and from 0.10 to 0.34 mg L^{-1} for TN (n=6).

Table 24. Lakes belonging to type L3.

SWB code	SWB name	Category	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG3AR800L041	Smolyanski ezera lakes	natural	1346	0.1	–
BG3MA600L138	Golyam Beglik dam	HMWB	1531	4.0	21
BG3MA900L192	Batak dam	HMWB	1103	21.0	15
BG3MA900L205	Belmeken dam	HMWB	1950	3.8	39
BG4DO600L119	Shiroka Polyana dam	HMWB	1525	4.0	–
BG4ST900L1001	Studena Dam	HMWB	846	1.2	20

Table 25. Reference values and class boundaries for TP ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to type L3. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Boundary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types				Proposal
			most probably range		median other MS		
			shallow polymictic	type 8 mean depth <15 m, calc.	type 8 mean depth >15 m, calc.	type 7 mid-alt., siliceous	
Reference							4
H/G	12.5	na	9–14	5–8			8
G/M	40	na	22–27	11–15	16	30	16
M/P							30
P/B							60

Table 26. Reference values and class boundaries for TN (mg L^{-1}) in lakes belonging to type L3. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Boundary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types				Proposal
			most probably range		median other MS		
			shallow polymictic	type 8 mean depth <15 m, calc.	type 8 mean depth >15 m, calc.	type 7 mid-alt., siliceous	
Reference							0.1
H/G	0.2	0.2	na	na	na	na	0.2
G/M	0.8	0.8	na	na	0.43	na	0.8
M/P							2.0
P/B							4.0

L4 Lowland & semi-mountain lakes and swamps in ER 12

Lake type L4 comprises three water bodies, two of them heavily modified, one artificial (Table 27). Another “L4 lake” is the Dragoman Marsh, which is part of the river SWB Nishava (Ginska) NVRWB1001 with SWB code BG1NV200R1001.

Marinov *et al.* (2021a) in their lake typology report considered L4 as oligo-mesotrophic without anthropogenic impact. The analyses carried out in the WB sister project on diffuse pollution allowed suggesting boundaries (Wolfram 2021a). At least Rabisha (with a mean depth of 18 m) resembles the broad lake type 8 *sensu* Solheim *et al.* (2019) and the difference from L2 is not fully clear, both in terms of altitude, size and depth, and in terms of geology (electric conductivity: 183–670 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, n=4). Choklyovo marsh lake and Dragoman Marsh differ from this type today. Based on historical data the four lakes share the following common characteristics:

- Origin carstic/tectonic
- Water sources mainly groundwater and atmospheric waters
- Area: much greater in the beginning of the 20th century (Choklyovo: 450 ha, Dragomansko: 400 ha, Skalensko: 89.6 ha, Rabishko Lake: 150 ha).

Before the 1930ies, Choklyovo lake was 450 ha large, during the 1930ies it decreased to about 200 ha. At that time, it was classified as a mountain morass and not as a typical swamp. This wetland functioned as a peatery and was completely dried out between 1950 and 1981. In 1981, the drainage system was removed and the peat bog began to flood again.

Dragomansko blato started to drain-out in 1981 (Kochev & Iordanov 1981). Till the end of 1980ies it was completely drained-out. After the economic changes in Bulgaria in the beginning of 1990ies, when the water pumping stopped, the swamp began naturally to restore itself. The filling-up with atmospheric waters still continues and the bog has not reached up the maximum depth it had at the beginning of the 20th century (1.5 m until the 1930ies; Michev & Stoyneva, unpubl.). The mass development of insectivorous plants up to the 1930s suggests some nitrogen limitation of primary productivity in the bog. However, no chemical data are available from that time to confirm this hypothesis.

Skalensko lake has shown a rather fast succession. In the 1920ies and 1930ies, G. Bonchev and D. Iordanoff described the lake as a water body with a surface area of 89.6 ha (Bonchev 1929; 1939; Iordanoff 1930-1931; 1938-1939), whereas in 1964 it was estimated to be only 44.4 ha. In the 1930ies, the depth still was 3–4 m. Most probably, due to the different successional stages in which it was described, different classification names were given to the water body: lake, karstic swamp, etc.

In the middle of the 20th century, Rabisha lake was finally successional transformed to a swamp. The process of silting-up and plant growth accelerated after the 1940ies due to meteorological conditions (hot and dry years in the period 1943–1952) and anthropogenic impacts (landslip from arable land; pumping-out of water for irrigation needs during the summer periods). The lake had a depth of 5 m in 1931, 2.5 m in 1936, and 0.95 m in 1952. At the same time, surface area decreased (from 150 ha in the 1930ies to 95 ha in the 1950ies) and the reed beds increased (extremely narrow in the 1930ies, quite wide in the 1950ies/1960ies). Like Skalensko lake, also Rabisha lake was called karstic bog, swamp and lake in different times by different authors. In 1962 it was transformed into a reservoir.

Table 27. Lakes belonging to type L4. Data on maximum depth from field measurements and after Stoyneva & Michev (2007).

SWB code	SWB name	Category	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m	max depth m
BG1WO300L018	Rabisha WOLWB018	HMWB	278	2.4	18	25
BG2KA400L044	Scala 1 dam	AWB	498	0.7	3.5	6–7
BG4ST900L1012	Choklyovo marsh lake	HMWB	860	0.9	1–1.2	2.3
BG1NV200R1001	Dragoman Marsh	natural	718	4.0	–	1

Based on these findings and taking into account the values suggested for L1 and L2, we propose a mean annual TP concentration of 6 µg L⁻¹ as reference value and 12 and 30 µg L⁻¹ as H/G and G/M boundaries, respectively (Table 28). The values in Ordinance H-4 seem too high and not sufficiently strict to prevent ecological deterioration. For TN, a slightly lower G/M boundary as given in the

Ordinance H-4 seems more appropriate. The other boundaries are derived in the same way as for the previous lake types based on expert judgment (Table 29).

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in L4 lakes range from below the LOD ($10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) to $58 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for TP (n=5) and from 0.26 to 2.21 mg L^{-1} for TN (n=5).

Table 28. Reference values and class boundaries for TP ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to type L4. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound-ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	most probable range			median other MS		Proposal
			type 8 mean depth <15 m, calc.	type 8 mean depth >15 m, calc.	type 3 lowland, calc.,mixed	type 8 mid-alt., calc/mix	type 3 lowland, calc.,mixed	
Ref.								6
H/G	25	–	9–14	5–8	22-32			12
G/M	75	–	22–27	11–15	35-44	16	30	30
M/P								60
P/B								120

Table 29. Reference values and class boundaries for TN (mg L^{-1}) in lakes belonging to type L4. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound-ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types					Proposal
			most probable range			median other MS		
			type 8 mean depth <15 m, calc.	type 8 mean depth >15 m, calc.	type 3 lowland, calc.,mixed	type 8 mid-alt., calc/mix	type 3 lowland, calc.,mixed	
Ref.								0.4
H/G	0.7	–	na	na	0.2–0.6			0.7
G/M	2.5	2?	na	na	1.0–2.1	na	1.63	2.0
M/P								4.0
P/B								8.0

L5 Riparian lakes and marshes in ER 12-1

L5a Riparian marshes in ER 12-2

The natural lakes belonging to L5 were split into two subtypes during the last C project 2015/2016, one of them represented only by Lake Srebarna (L5), the other one by Lake Arkutino and Velyov vir (L5a) (Table 30). Lake Srebarna was successfully intercalibrated (Borics *et al.* 2018). No TP values exist for these lakes in the national Ordinance H-4 (MoEW 2020). In the lake typology report submitted with the IV Progress Report, Marinov *et al.* (2021a) suggested that L5 was naturally eutrophic and L5a naturally hypertrophic. The shallow character (polymictic?) as well as also the sporadic impact of external water support this view. Both lake types can be assigned to the broad lake type 4 “Lowland, calcareous/mixed, very shallow, unstratified” *sensu* Solheim *et al.* (2019), although the peculiarities of the three BG lakes make direct comparison with other shallow lakes difficult.

Summarising the existing information we propose a mean annual TP concentration of $30 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ as reference value, assuming that submerged macrophytes in these lakes can have a significant impact on nutrient availability. Shallow lakes and shallow flood plain in Central Europe can have even lower mean TP concentrations if nutrient loads are low and macrophyte the dominant primary producers (Donabaum & Riedler 2018; Teubner *et al.* 2018). 50 and $100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ are suggested as H/G and G/M boundaries, respectively (Table 31). It should be stressed though that such high TP concentrations have little relevance in the ecological classification of lakes at hypertrophic conditions. The classification should rather rely on other BQE than phytoplankton.

TN boundaries are suggested similar to L4. The G/M boundary is higher than the median in lakes from other MS belonging to the broad types 3, 4 and 6, but within the most probable range as defined by Phillips *et al.* (2018) (Table 32).

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in L5a lakes range from 141 to $910 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for TP (n=2) and from 0.45 to 4.11 mg L^{-1} for TN (n=2).

Table 30. Lakes belonging to type L5 / L5a.

SWB code	SWB name	type	Category	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG1DU000L1003	Srebarna DULWB1003	L5	natural	11	6.3	<3?
BG2IU200L019	Arcoutino lake	L5a	natural	22	0.3	<3?
BG2IU200R1005	Veliov vir Lake	L5a	natural	11		<3?

Table 31. Reference values and class boundaries for TP ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to type L5 / L5a. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound- ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types					Proposal
			most probable range		median other MS			
			type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mix unstratified	type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mixed unstratified	type 6 lowland, organic or calc/mix	
Ref.								30
H/G	–	–	22-32	32-35				50
G/M	–	–	35-44	45-70	39	60	24	100
M/P								200
P/B								500

Table 32. Reference values and class boundaries for TN (mg L^{-1}) in lakes belonging to type L5 / L5a. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probable range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound-ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types					Proposal
			most probable range		median other MS			
			type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mix unstratified	type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mixed unstratified	type 6 lowland, organic or calc/mix	
Ref.								0.4
H/G	–	–	0.2–0.6	na				0.7
G/M	–	–	1.0–2.1	na	1.63	1.15	1.10	2.0
M/P								4.0
P/B								8.0

L6 Riparian wetlands in ER 7

No SWB is assigned as such to the BG national lake type L6. However, three sites were sampled in 2020, which correspond to this lake type though they are part of a river SWB. They are located along the large rivers Maritsa and Mesta, respectively (Table 33). It is doubtful whether the broad lake types as defined by Solheim *et al.* (2019) cover these specific wetlands. Either the broad type 3 and 4 or broad type 15 (Mediterranean, very small) could share some similarities with the BG type L6. In the national ordinance H-4 (MoEW 2020), high values like for L4 are given, which complies with the statement in Marinov *et al.* (2021a) that these lakes are hypertrophic. More data on size, depth, substrate, macrophyte cover and the hydrological conditions (regular flooding?) could give more insight. For the time being, the same reference value and class boundaries as for L5/L5a are proposed (Table 34). Also for TN, the boundaries derived for L4 and L5 can be accepted (Table 35).

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in L6 lakes range from 91 to 656 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for TP (n=2) and from 1.93 to 9.66 mg L^{-1} for TN (n=2).

Table 33. Lakes belonging to type L6.

SWB code	SWB name	Lake name	Category	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG3MA350R211	Maritsa river from Chepelarska river to Omurovska river	Krairechna Murtvitsa Lake near v. Popovitsa	natural	132	–	<3?
BG3MA350R212	Maritsa river from flow to Omurovska river to flow to Sazliyka river	Protected Area "Zlatopole"(old meander of Maritsa River)	natural	94	–	<3?
BG4ME500R107	Mesta from the confluence of the Kanina River to the confluence of the Matnitsa River	Riparian Wetlands near Gotse Delchev (Mesta river)	HMWB	484	–	<3?

Table 34. Reference values and class boundaries for TP ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to type L6. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound-ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	most probable range		median other MS			Proposal
			type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mix unstratified	type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mixed unstratified	type 15 Mediterran. very small	
Ref.								30
H/G	25	–	22-32	32-35				50
G/M	75	–	35-44	45-70	39	60	26	100
M/P								200
P/B								500

Table 35. Reference values and class boundaries for TN (mg L^{-1}) in lakes belonging to type L6. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound-ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types					Proposal	
			most probable range		median other MS				
			type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mix unstratified	type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mixed unstratified	type 15 Mediterran. very small		
Ref.									0.4
H/G	0.7	–	0.2–0.6	na					0.7
G/M	2.5	2.0?	1.0–2.1	na	1.63	1.15	na		2.0
M/P									4.0
P/B									8.0

L7 (new code: TFL7) Black Sea coastal freshwater lakes

L8 (new code: TOL8) Black Sea coastal oligohaline lakes

Among the 129 SWB defined as lakes, three are assigned to the lake type L7, two of them as HMWB, while four are assigned to lake type L8 (Table 36). The L7 lakes are freshwater lakes though located near the Black Sea and considered as transitional. The electric conductivity measurements in 2020 ranged from 581 to 2040 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ (n=3). L8 lakes are oligohaline (Cheshmedjiev *et al.* 2010) with significant higher electric conductivities: in 2020 between 1069 and 5620 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ (n=3). No data on depth is available, but according to Cheshmedjiev *et al.* (2010) mean depth of both lake types is <3 m.

Cheshmedjiev *et al.* (2010) describe L7 and L8 lakes as meso- to eutrophic, Marinov *et al.* (2021a) as naturally hypertrophic. In the national ordinance H-4 high concentrations for TP are defined for the H/G and G/M boundaries (MoEW 2020), which seemed acceptable in the analysis of the WB sister project on diffuse pollution (Wolfram 2021a). Comparability with the broad lake types *sensu* Solheim *et al.* (2019) is limited, although they share characteristics of type 3 (lowland stratified) and 4 (lowland unstratified).

Based on these findings we propose to slightly adapt the class boundaries as defined in the national Ordinance H-4 (higher for H/G, lower for G/M). The corresponding reference value is set by expert judgment, the class boundaries for M/P and P/B are defined as twice as high as the better status boundary in each case (Table 37). The proposed boundaries in L7 and L8 lakes, thus, are the same as for L5/L5a and L6. For TN, the currently legally binding boundaries are accepted, while the reference and the lower boundaries are derived in the same way as for previous lake types (factor 2 by expert judgment; Table 38).

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in L7 and L8 lakes range from 16 to 660 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for TP (n=16) and from 0.37 to 5.23 mg L^{-1} for TN (n=13).

Table 36. Lakes belonging to type L7 and L8.

SWB code	SWB name	Category	Type	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG2DO700L017	Durankulak lake	natural	L7	0	2.5	–
BG2DO700L018	Shabla lake and Ezeretsko lake	natural	L7	4	2.7	–
BG2MA107L002	Mandra dam	HMWB	L7	29	33.0	–
BG2IU200L007	Stamopolu lake	natural	L8	68	0.04	–
BG2IU200L017	Alepu lake	natural	L8	66	1.1	–
BG2IU600L018	Devil's swamp	natural	L8	3	0.1	–
BG2SE900L037	Burgasko lake	HMWB	L8	1	25.4	–

Table 37. Reference values and class boundaries for TP ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to type L7 and L8. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound- ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types					Proposal
			most probable range		median other MS			
			type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mix unstratified	type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mixed unstratified	type 15 Mediterran. very small	
Ref.								20
H/G	25	25?	22-32	32-35				30
G/M	75	75?	35-44	45-70	39	60	26	60
M/P								120
P/B								240

Table 38. Reference values and class boundaries for TN (mg L^{-1}) in lakes belonging to type L7 and L8. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probable range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound-ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types					Proposal
			most probable range		median other MS			
			type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mix unstratified	type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mixed unstratified	type 15 Mediterran. Mediterran. very small	
Ref.								0.4
H/G	0.7	–	0.2–0.6	na				0.7
G/M	2.5	–	1.0–2.1	na	1.63	1.15	na	2.5
M/P								5.0
P/B								10.0

L9 (new code: TMPL9) Black Sea coastal mesohaline and polyhaline lakes

L10 (new code: THL10) Black Sea coastal hyperhaline lakes

6 SWB are currently assigned to L9 and two SWB to L10 (Table 39). Both types are transitional waters with significantly enhanced salinities. The range of the measurements of electric conductivity and salinity in the campaigns 2020 was:

L9: 18,400–28,300 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ and 10.7–17.5‰ (n=8)

L10: 30,800–54,200 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ and 19.2–36.0‰ (n=4)

This complies roughly with the description in Cheshmedjiev *et al.* (2010) who list as optional factors for L9 “30‰ mesohaline & polyhaline; equal to Black Sea” and for L10 “>40‰ superhaline”. These figures are also included of the national ordinance H-4, which means that the measurements from 2020 deviate from the type-specific, mandatory salinity ranges.

In terms of trophic state, L10 are classified as eu- to polytrophic in Cheshmedjiev *et al.* (2010). In the Diffuse Pollution Project, the high boundaries as given in the national Ordinance H-4 (MoEW 2020) were accepted as reasonable (Wolfram 2021a). For harmonisation with other types, we propose to raise the G/M boundary, which should not be lower (stricter) for L9 and L10 than for the lake type L5 to L8. For TN, the currently legally binding boundaries are accepted, while the reference and the lower boundaries are derived in the same way as for previous lake types (factor 2 by expert judgment; Table 41).

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in L9 and L10 lakes range from 34 to 551 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for TP (n=23) and from 0.39 to 2.45 mg L^{-1} for TN (n=23).

Table 39. Lakes belonging to type L9 and L10.

SWB code	SWB name	Category	Type	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG2MA100L001	Mandra lake	HMWB	L9	8	1.9	
BG2PR100L001	Varnensko lake	HMWB	L9	58	15.7	–
BG2PR100L002	Canal between Beloslavsko lake and Varnensko lake	HMWB	L9	104	1.5	–
BG2PR100L003	Beloslavsko lake	HMWB	L9	1	7.3	–
BG2PR900L019	Old canal between Varnensko lake and Bleak sea	HMWB	L9	3	0.1	–
BG2PR900L020	New canal between Varnensko lake and Bleak sea	AWB	L9	4	0.3	–
BG2SE900L027	Atanasovsko lake	HMWB	L10	26	9.7	–
BG2SE900L028	Pomoriisko lake	HMWB	L10	21	6.0	–

Table 40. Reference values and class boundaries for TP ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to type L9 and L10. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound- ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types					Proposal
			most probable range		median other MS			
			type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mix unstratified	type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mixed unstratified	type 15 Mediterran. Mediterran. very small	
Ref.								20
H/G	25	25?	22-32	32-35				30
G/M	75	75?	35-44	45-70	39	60	26	75
M/P								150
P/B								300

Table 41. Reference values and class boundaries for TN (mg L^{-1}) in lakes belonging to type L9 and L10. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound- ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types					Proposal
			most probable range		median other MS			
			type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mix unstratified	type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 4 lowland, calc/mixed unstratified	type 15 Mediterran. Mediterran. very small	
Ref.								0.4
H/G	na	–	0.2–0.6	na				0.7
G/M	na	–	1.0–2.1	na	1.63	1.15	na	2.5
M/P								5.0
P/B								10.0

L11a (new code: RL11a) Large (>10 km²) mid-altitude (200-800 m asl) reservoirs in ER 12

L11b (RL11b) Large (>10 km²) mid-altitude (200-400 m asl) reservoirs in ER 7

L12 (RL12) Small to medium-sized (<10 km²) mid-altitude (200-800 m asl) reservoirs in ER12

L13 (RL13) Small to medium-sized (<10 km²) mid-altitude (200-800 m asl) reservoirs in ER 7

2 SWB each are assigned to lake type L11a and 5 SWB to lake type L11b, which include large deep mid-altitude reservoirs (HMWB) in the ER 12 (L11a) and ER 7 (L11b) (Table 42). All reservoirs can be assumed to be stratified, hence, resembling the natural broad lake type 8 *sensu* Solheim *et al.* (2019). A direct comparison of the national types with the broad types is difficult, since the broad lake types include also geology, which is only partly considered in the national typology in BG.

Reservoir types L12 and L13 include small to medium-sized reservoirs (HMWB, some AWB) within the same range of altitude as L11a/L11b. The surface area varies between 0.3–7.2 km². Mean depth is available from most SWB and ranges from 5 to 46 m (Table 42; 2 exceptions with 2 m). Apart from the two exceptions it can be assumed that the L12 and L13 lakes/reservoirs are stratified.

In their lake typology report, Marinov *et al.* (2021a) grouped the lake types L11, L12 and L13 into the oligo-mesotrophic class, while the analysis in the Diffuse Pollution Project suggested oligotrophic conditions (Wolfram 2021a) and classified the H/G boundary and even more so the G/M boundary of the Ordinance H-4 as too high. The oligo-mesotrophic reference state can be accepted for the group of mid-altitude reservoirs (L11a, L11b, L12, L13), while oligotrophic conditions are justified for high-altitude (see below). Based on these findings and taking into account the values suggested the broad types by Phillips & Pitt (2016) and Phillips *et al.* (2018) we propose a mean annual TP concentration of 8 µg L⁻¹ as reference value and 16 and 35 µg L⁻¹ as H/G and G/M boundaries, respectively, for all four sub-types (Table 43). These values are close to those for L4, which are also considered as naturally oligo-mesotrophic by Marinov *et al.* (2021a). For TN, we also suggest to apply the boundaries derived for L4 (Table 44).

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in lakes of this group of types range from below LOD (10 µg L⁻¹) to 540 µg L⁻¹ for TP (n=35) and from 0.10 to 1.675 mg L⁻¹ for TN (n=33).

Table 42. Lakes belonging to type L11a, L11b, L12 and L13 (mid-altitude reservoirs).

SWB code	SWB name	Category	ER	Type	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG2KA400L024	Kamchia dam	HMWB	12	L11a	256	9.6	24
BG1IS700L1005	Iskar ISRWB1005	HMWB	12	L11a	814	27.6	24
BG3AR350L010	Studen kladenets dam	HMWB	7	L11b	218	31.1	13
BG3AR570L021	dam Kardzhali	HMWB	7	L11b	307	16.4	30
BG3TU700L036	Zhrebchevo dam	HMWB	7	L11b	260	19.1	21
BG3TU900L047	Koprinka dam	HMWB	7	L11b	381	11.4	13
BG3MA500L119	Pyasachnik dam	HMWB	7	L11b	283	12.5	16
BG1IS500L1008	Pancharevo ISRWB1008	HMWB	12	L12	597	0.7	9
BG1OG700L1016	Rechenska Bara OGLWB1016	HMWB	12	L12	450	0.8	20
BG1RL200L1002	Boyka RLRWB1002	HMWB	12	L12	253	0.5	

SWB code	SWB name	Category	ER	Type	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG1OG600L1015	Dabnika OGLWB1015	HMWB	12	L12	341	1.1	
BG1RL200L1006	Kavatsite RLRWB1006	HMWB	12	L12	206	0.6	
BG1RL900L1009	Beli Lom RLRWB1009	HMWB	12	L12	279	2.8	9
BG1RL900L1011	Lomtsi RLRWB1011	HMWB	12	L12	205	0.6	
BG1VT800L1004	Sopot VTRWB1004	HMWB	12	L12	365	3.4	18
BG1WO200L1003	Kula WORWB1003	HMWB	12	L12	202	1.2	16
BG1WO300L1006	Poletkovtsi WORWB1006	HMWB	12	L12	201	0.5	
BG1YN400L1005	Krapets YNRWB1005	HMWB	12	L12	407	1.3	
BG1YN600L1024	Yestrebino YNRWB1024	HMWB	12	L12	337	5.4	11
BG1VT300L1010	Telish VTRWB1010	HMWB	12	L12	216	1.3	
BG2KA900L036	Cherkovna dam	HMWB	12	L12	281	0.6	
BG2KA800L032	Polyanitza dam	AWB	12	L12	238	0.7	
BG1IS700L1306	Kokalyane_ISRWB1306	HMWB	12	L12	695	0.4	
BG3MA300L061	Mechka_dam	HMWB	7	L13	324	0.3	25
BG3AR400L015	Benkovski dam	HMWB	7	L13	408	0.5	
BG3AR600L025	Borovitsa dam WS	HMWB	7	L13	482	1.0	27
BG3MA600L132	Krichim dam	HMWB	7	L13	415	0.7	29
BG3MA600L133	Vacha dam	HMWB	7	L13	541	4.9	46
BG3MA800L163	Bakar dere dam	HMWB	7	L13	741	0.8	
BG3TU500L013	Malko Sharkovo dam	HMWB	7	L13	235	2.9	16
BG3TU700L030	Asenovets dam WS	HMWB	7	L13	414	1.1	26
BG4ST500L1006	Stoykovtsy dam	HMWB	7	L13	628	2.8	
BG4ST700L1002	Drenov Dol dam	HMWB	7	L13	542	0.4	
BG4ST900L014	Izvor Dam	HMWB	7	L13	689	0.7	
BG4ST900L1005	Dyakovo dam	HMWB	7	L13	662	2.1	17
BG4ST900L1008	Dolna Dikanja dam	HMWB	7	L13	708	0.7	
BG4ST900L1010	Pchelina Dam	HMWB	7	L13	620	5.7	9
BG3MA400L213	Domlyan dam	HMWB	7	L13	344	1.5	17
BG3MA800L160	Topolnitsa dam	HMWB	7	L13	376	7.2	19
BG3MA100L012	Trakiets_dam	HMWB	7	L13	245	4.7	24
BG3MA300L045	Garvanovo_dam	HMWB	7	L13	212	2.8	9
BG3TU900L043	Fisheries_-_Nikolaevo_village	AWB	7	L13	264	2.1	
BG3MA300L058	Lenovo_dam	HMWB	7	L13	335	0.4	16
BG3MA400L086	Sinyata_reka_dam	HMWB	7	L13	301	0.4	5
BG3MA400L084	Chernozem_reservoir	AWB	7	L13	247	0.5	7
BG3MA300L073	40-te_izvora_dam	HMWB	7	L13	236	0.5	8
BG3MA400L081	Novo_Zhelezare_dam	AWB	7	L13	282	0.5	6
BG3MA300L051	Bryagovo_1_dam	HMWB	7	L13	283	0.6	14
BG3MA500L125	Kavaka_dam	AWB	7	L13	299	0.8	2
BG3MA400L215	Tsarimir_dam	AWB	7	L13	230	0.9	2
BG3MA300L074	Syshitsa_dam	HMWB	7	L13	434	0.4	11
BG3MA400L092	Svezhen dam	HMWB	7	L13	810	0.04	

SWB code	SWB name	Category	ER	Type	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG3MA800L180	Dushanci dam	HMWB	7	L13	774	0.7	
BG3MA600L134	Tsankov kamak dam	HMWB	7	L13	680	7.1	16

Table 43. Reference values and class boundaries for TP ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to the types L11a, L11b, L12a and L13a (mid-altitude reservoirs). Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound-ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Median other MS (Broad European types)					Proposal
			type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 7 mid- altitude, siliceous	type 8 mid- altitude, calc/mix	type 13 Med., siliceous (incl. res.)	type 14 Med., calc/mix	
Ref.								8
H/G	12.5	<12.5						16
G/M	40	<<40	39	16	30	42	23	35
M/P								70
P/B								140

Table 44. Reference values and class boundaries for TN (mg L^{-1}) in lakes belonging to the types L11a, L11b, L12a and L13a (mid-altitude reservoirs). Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound-ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Median other MS (Broad European types)					Proposal
			type 3 lowland, calc/mix stratified	type 7 mid- altitude, siliceous	type 8 mid- altitude, calc/mix	type 13 Med., siliceous (incl. res.)	type 14 Med., calc/mix	
Ref.								0.1
H/G	0.2							0.2
G/M	0.8		1.63	0.43	na	na	na	0.8
M/P								2.0
P/B								4.0

L11c (new code: RL11c) Large (>10 km²) high-altitude (>1,000 m asl) reservoirs in ER 7

Only one reservoir – Dospat reservoir – lies at an altitude above 800 m asl (Table 45). It is large and deep (subtype L11c) and can be assumed to be stratified, hence, resembling the natural broad lake type 11 or 12 *sensu* Solheim *et al.* (2019).

In their lake typology report, Marinov *et al.* (2021a) grouped the lake type L11 into the oligo-mesotrophic class, while the analysis in the Diffuse Pollution Project suggested oligotrophic conditions (Wolfram 2021a) and classified the H/G boundary and even more so the G/M boundary for TP in the Ordinance H-4 ($40 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) as too high. As stated above, due to the higher altitude a lower trophic state of the high-altitude Dospat reservoir is likely.

Based on these findings and taking into account the values suggested the broad types by Phillips & Pitt (2016) we propose the same nutrient reference values and class boundaries as for the mountain lakes of type L3 (Table 46 & Table 47).

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in Dospat reservoir (from different years and sampling points) range from 8 to 61 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for TP (n=4) and from 0.58 to 0.97 mg L^{-1} for TN (n=4).

Table 45. Lakes belonging to type L11c (high-altitude reservoirs).

SWB code	SWB name	Category	ER	Type	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG4DO900L117	Dospat dam	HMWB	7	L11c	1199	19.6	23

Table 46. Reference values and class boundaries for TP ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to the type L11c (high-altitude reservoirs). Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Boundary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Median other MS (Broad European types)		Proposal
			type 11 <i>Highland, siliceous</i>	type 12 <i>Highland, calc./mixed</i>	
Ref.					4
H/G	12.5	<12.5			8
G/M	40	<<40	16	15	16
M/P					30
P/B					60

Table 47. Reference values and class boundaries for TN (mg L^{-1}) in lakes belonging to the type L11c (high-altitude reservoirs). Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Boundary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Median other MS (Broad European types)		Proposal
			type 11 <i>Highland, siliceous</i>	type 12 <i>Highland, calc./mixed</i>	
Ref.					0.1
H/G	0.2	0.2			0.2
G/M	0.8	1.0		0.25	0.8
M/P					2.0
P/B					4.0

L14 (new code: RL14) Large (>5 km²) lowland (<20 m asl) reservoirs up to middle depth in ER 12

Only 5 SWB currently belong to the lake type L14 (Table 48). They differ from L12 and L13 by altitude and from the next type (L15) by ecoregion. The altitude justifies a slightly higher trophic reference state as compared with L11–L13.

In their lake typology report, Marinov *et al.* (2021a) grouped the lake type L14 into the mesotrophic class, which was supported by the analysis in the Diffuse Pollution Project (Wolfram 2021a). Based on the analysis in this project, the values from Ordinance H-4 for H/G (25 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) seems reasonable,

while the G/M boundary ($75 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) was considered as too high. The L14 reservoirs resemble the European broad type 3.

Based on these findings and taking into account the values suggested the broad types by Phillips & Pitt (2016) we propose a TP reference values of $25 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and class boundaries of 50 and $100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for H/G and G/M, respectively (Table 46 & Table 47).

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in L14 lakes range from below LOD ($10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) to $134 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for TP (n=8) and from 0.325 to 1.030 mg L^{-1} for TN (n=8).

Table 48. Lakes belonging to type L14.

SWB code	SWB name	ER	Category	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG1VT300L1012	Gorni Dabnik VTRWB1012	12	HMWB	171	5.1	26
BG2KA400L008	Tsonevo dam	12	HMWB	59	15.6	
BG1YN400L1009	Alexandar Stamboliyski YNRWB1009	12	HMWB	186	9.8	21
BG1OG700L1004	Ogosta OGRWB1004	12	HMWB	189	17.3	29
BG2KA900L021	Ticha dam	12	HMWB	184	18.4	17

Table 49. Reference values and class boundaries for TP ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to the type L14. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound-ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types		Proposal
			most probable range	Median other MS	
			type 3 <i>Lowland, calc./mix, stratified</i>	type 3 <i>Lowland, calc./mix, stratified</i>	
Ref.					12
H/G	25	25	22–32		25
G/M	75	<<75	35–44	39	50
M/P					100
P/B					200

Table 50. Reference values and class boundaries for TN ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to the type L14. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound-ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Broad European types		Proposal
			most probable range	Median other MS	
			type 3 <i>Lowland, calc./mix, stratified</i>	type 3 <i>Lowland, calc./mix, stratified</i>	
Ref.					0.4
H/G	0.7	–	0.2–0.6		0.7
G/M	2.5	<2.5	1.0–2.1	1.63	2.0
M/P					4.0
P/B					8.0

L15 (new code: RL15) Large (>5 km²) lowland (<200 m asl) reservoirs in ER 7

3 SWB of this type are situated below 200 m asl. They resemble L14 reservoirs but are located in ER 7. Based on a former data analysis, the L15 reservoirs are expected to be meso-eutrophic without significant anthropogenic impact in organic or nutrient pollution. However, as the L15 reservoirs have a mean depth of around 5–10 m, strong water level fluctuations (WLF) can affect the physico-chemical conditions and raise the trophic state based on this physical alteration and independent of enhanced external nutrient inputs. On the other hand, based on the similarity with R14 they R15 reservoirs be rather placed within the main trophic group of mesotrophic lakes.

Among the broad types *sensu* Solheim *et al.* (2019), type 13 and 14 show some similarities with the reservoirs of the BG type L15, although altitude is not considered for these types. Comparability with the BG reservoirs of L15 is thus limited.

Taking into account all available data we propose 12, 25 and 50 g L⁻¹ for TP annual mean as reference values, H/G class boundary and G/M class boundary, respectively. Taking into account the WLF, the concentrations for the EP can be set at 15, 30 and 60 µg L⁻¹ (like for the next types L16 and L17, see below).

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in L15 lakes (only 1 year from Rozov kladenec is available) are 682 µg L⁻¹ TP and 2.888 mg L⁻¹ TN (n=1).

Table 51. Lakes belonging to type L15.

SWB code	SWB name	Category	ER	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG3MA200L210	Ovcharitsa dam	HMWB	BG3	133	9.4	5
BG3AR100L004	Ivaylovgrad dam	HMWB	BG3	120	18.3	9
BG3MA200L019	Rozov kladenets dam	AWB	BG3	102	5.5	4

Table 52. Reference values and class boundaries for TP (µg L⁻¹) in lakes belonging to the type L15. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Boundary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Median other MS (Broad European types)		Proposal
			type 13 <i>Mediterranean, siliceous</i>	type 14 <i>Mediterranean, calc./mixed</i>	
Ref.					12
H/G	25	25			25
G/M	75	<<75	42	23	50
M/P					100
P/B					200

Table 53. Reference values and class boundaries for TN ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to the type L15. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Boundary	Ord. H-4	Diff.Poll.	Median other MS (Broad European types)		Proposal
			type 13 <i>Mediterranean, siliceous</i>	type 14 <i>Mediterranean, calc./mixed</i>	
Ref.					0.4
H/G	0.7	–			0.7
G/M	2.5	<2.5	<i>na</i>	<i>na</i>	2.0
M/P					4.0
P/B					8.0

L16 (new code: RL16) Small to medium-sized (<5 km²) lowland (<200 m asl) reservoirs in ER 12

L17 (new code: RL17) Small to medium-sized (<5 km²) lowland (<200 m asl) reservoirs in ER 7

The last two types of reservoirs are situated in the lowland and differ from the previous types L14 and L15 by size. Some of them are deep, while others are rather shallow with mean depths around 1 m (calculated from volume and surface area) and a maximum depth of round 4–6 m. This justifies to assume a higher trophic state for these reservoirs, which is confirmed by the data on the European broad lake types. Like for other types above, the comparability with the broad types is limited though; the BG reservoirs L16 and L17 resemble to some extent the broad types 3 and 4 (stratified/unstratified lowland, calcareous/mixed), but L17 could also be assigned to the broad types 14 (Mediterranean with calcareous geology).

Based on the data analysis and taking into account the information on European broad types, we propose a reference value, H/G and G/M class boundary for TP of 15, 30 and 60 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

For comparison – current annual mean concentrations in L16 and L17 lakes range from 14 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ to >2 mg L^{-1} for TP (n=23) and from 0.35 to 18.6 mg L^{-1} for TN (n=22).

Table 54. Lakes belonging to type L16 and L17.

SWB code	SWB name	ER	Category	Type	Altitude m asl	Area km ²	avg depth m
BG2SE900L032	Troyanovo dam	12	HMWB	L16	90	1.0	
BG1WO800L021	Kovachitsa WOLWB021	12	AWB	L16	111	1.0	
BG1DU000L1002	Antimovo DURWB1002	12	AWB	L16	97	1.1	
BG2MA600L016	Krushovo dam	12	HMWB	L16	105	1.7	
BG2PR300L021	Trastikovo dam	12	AWB	L16	49	1.9	
BG1WO800L1020	Rasovo WORWB1020	12	HMWB	L16	133	0.4	
BG2MA600L017	Kartelka dam	12	HMWB	L16	105	0.5	
BG1DJ345L1014	Onogur DJRWB1014	12	HMWB	L16	85	0.6	
BG1DU000L1001	Asparuhov val DULWB1001	12	AWB	L16	100	0.9	
BG2SE800L018	Aheloi dam	12	HMWB	L16	149	0.7	19
BG2SE600L016	Poroi dam	12	HMWB	L16	39	1.8	25
BG1RL200L1004	Baniska RLRWB1004	12	HMWB	L16	154	1.7	
BG2KA200L006	Eleshnitsa dam	12	HMWB	L16	58	0.9	
BG2IU400L011	Yasna Polyana dam	12	HMWB	L16	92	2.1	15
BG2KA800L027	Fisek dam	12	HMWB	L16	174	1.2	
BG2KA800L029	Saedinenie dam	12	HMWB	L16	175	2.5	5
BG1WO600L1014	Hristo Smirnenski WORWB1014	12	HMWB	L16	151	0.8	
BG3MA200L031	Radnevo dam	7	HMWB	L17	112	1.0	1.4
BG3MA300L041	Byalo pole 1 dam	7	HMWB	L17	140	1.1	1.0
BG3TU200L010	Roza 3 dam	7	HMWB	L17	140	1.1	0.9
BG3MA200L032	Daskal Atanasovo dam	7	HMWB	L17	120	1.4	0.8
BG3MA300L054	Chirpan dam	7	HMWB	L17	138	0.4	4
BG3MA200L021	Pastren dam	7	AWB	L17	148	0.4	7
BG3MA200L015	Troyan dam	7	HMWB	L17	145	0.6	11
BG3MA300L068	General Nikolaevo 1 dam	7	AWB	L17	200	0.8	5
BG3TU200L009	Malazmak dam	7	HMWB	L17	132	0.9	
BG3TU600L023	Tsanko_Tserkovski_dam	7	HMWB	L17	150	1.7	4
BG3MA300L065	Tyurkmen_dam_(Dalgana_dam)	7	HMWB	L17	184	0.5	8
BG3MA300L049	Ezerovo_dam	7	HMWB	L17	170	0.8	7
BG3TU500L017	Kirilovo dam	7	HMBW	L17	127	2.1	6

Table 55. Reference values and class boundaries for TP ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to the types L16 and L17. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound-ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.P oll.	Broad European types					Proposal
			most probable range		median other MS			
			type 3 Lowland, calc./mix, stratified	type 4 Lowland, calc./mix, unstrat.	type 3 Lowland, calc./mix, stratified	type 4 Lowland, calc./mix, unstratified	type 14 Lowland, calc./mix, stratified	
Ref.								15
H/G	25	25	22–32	32–35	na	na	na	30
G/M	75	<<75	35–44	45–70	39	60	23	60
M/P								120
P/B								240

Table 56. Reference values and class boundaries for TN ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in lakes belonging to the type L16 & L17. Sources ... Ordinance H-4: MoEW (2020), Diff.Poll.: Wolfram (2021a), most probably range: Phillips *et al.* (2018), median of other member states: Phillips & Pitt (2016).

Bound-ary	Ord. H-4	Diff.P oll.	Broad European types					Proposal
			most probable range		median other MS			
			type 3 Lowland, calc./mix, stratified	type 4 Lowland, calc./mix, unstrat.	type 3 Lowland, calc./mix, stratified	type 4 Lowland, calc./mix, unstratified	type 14 Lowland, calc./mix, stratified	
Ref.								0.4
H/G	0.7	–	0.2–0.6	na				0.7
G/M	2.5	<2.5	1.0–2.1	na	1.63	1.15	na	2.0
M/P								4.0
P/B								8.0

7.2 Transitional river type R16

Most transitional R16 rivers are stretches which have upstream rivers belonging to type R11. One exception is Veleka river (upstream river R10) and Rezovska river (R4). For R10 and R11, the national ordinance H-4 gives the following class boundaries for TP and TN:

TP	H/G	150 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	TN	H/G	1.0 mg L^{-1}
	G/M	300 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$		G/M	2.5 mg L^{-1}

For R4, lower boundaries are given:

TP	H/G	25 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	TN	H/G	0.5 mg L^{-1}
	G/M	75 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$		G/M	1.5 mg L^{-1}

The range of nutrient concentrations in the monitoring data from 2020 is for single dates:

- Range TP 10–882 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, TN 0.1–11.4 mg L^{-1}
- Median TP 73 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, TN 0.96 mg L^{-1}
- avg TP 189 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, TN 1.74 mg L^{-1}

and for annual means:

- Range TP 13–777 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, TN 0.38–6.9 mg L^{-1}
- Median TP 86 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, TN 0.60 mg L^{-1}
- avg TP 189 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, TN 1.74 mg L^{-1}

By expert judgment we propose the following boundaries.

TP	H/G	75 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	TN	H/G	0.7 mg L^{-1}
	G/M	150 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$		G/M	2.0 mg L^{-1}

Further class boundaries are defined by applying factor 2 to the G/M and the subsequent boundary.

The reference values is defined by expert judgment at 50 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for TP and 0.5 mg L^{-1} for TN.

7.3 Summary table

Table 57. Overview of proposed reference values and class boundaries for TP [$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$] and TN [mg L^{-1}] in BG lakes/reservoirs and transitional river type R16.

Trophic groups		Type		TP					TN				
main	sub	old	new	ref	HG	GM	MP	PB	ref	HG	GM	MP	PB
oligo	u-o	L01	L1	3	5	12	24	48	0.1	0.2	0.8	2.0	4.0
	o	L02	L2	4	8	16	30	60	0.1	0.2	0.8	2.0	4.0
	o	L03	L3	4	8	16	30	60	0.1	0.2	0.8	2.0	4.0
m	o-m	L04	L4	6	12	30	60	120	0.4	0.7	2.0	4.0	8.0
eu	e-h	L05	L5	30	50	100	200	500	0.4	0.7	2.0	4.0	8.0
	h	L05a	L5a	30	50	100	200	500	0.4	0.7	2.0	4.0	8.0
	h	L06	L6	30	50	100	200	500	0.4	0.7	2.0	4.0	8.0
	e-h	L07	TFL7	20	30	60	120	240	0.4	0.7	2.5	5.0	10.0
	e-h	L08	TOL8	20	30	60	120	240	0.4	0.7	2.5	5.0	10.0
-	-	L09	TMPL9	20	30	75	150	300	0.4	0.7	2.5	5.0	10.0
-	-	L10	THL10	20	30	75	150	300	0.4	0.7	2.5	5.0	10.0
m	o-m	L11a	RL11a	8	16	35	70	140	0.4	0.7	2.0	4.0	8.0
	o-m	L11b	RL11b	8	16	35	70	140	0.4	0.7	2.0	4.0	8.0
o	o	L11c	RL11c	4	8	16	30	60	0.1	0.2	0.8	2.0	4.0
meso	o-m	L12	RL12	8	16	35	70	140	0.1	0.2	0.8	2.0	4.0
	o-m	L13	RL13	8	16	35	70	140	0.1	0.2	0.8	2.0	4.0
	m	L14	RL14	12	25	50	100	200	0.4	0.7	2.0	4.0	8.0
	m	L15	RL15	12	25	50	100	200	0.4	0.7	2.0	4.0	8.0
eu	e	L16	RL16	15	30	60	120	240	0.4	0.7	2.0	4.0	8.0
	e	L17	RL17	15	30	60	120	240	0.4	0.7	2.0	4.0	8.0
-	-	R16	R16	50	75	150	300	600	0.5	0.7	2.0	4.0	8.0

8 Reference values and class boundaries for phytoplankton metrics in freshwater lakes/reservoirs (incl. L7 and oligohaline L8)

8.1 Chlorophyll-a and Q index in freshwater (and oligohaline) lakes and reservoirs

The nutrient boundaries defined above are the basis for deriving boundaries chlorophyll-a and the Q index. The multiple regression models with TP and TN as independent variables was used (*cf* Table 11) for chl and the regression model with TP for Q index. Chl-a concentrations above $20 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ are rounded to 0 digits.

For the lake type L5 (only Srebarina), the values from Borics *et al.* (2018) are given. Since L5a and L6 can be considered as comparable with L5 in terms of reference trophic state, the same chl-a concentrations are given for these types.

The values are in line with those suggested in Annex II of the IV BMR, but partly stricter than those given in the national Ordinance H-4. We recommend amending these values in the national legislation.

Table 58. Overview of proposed reference values and class boundaries for chlorophyll-a [$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$] and the Q index in BG freshwater lakes and reservoirs. For L9 and L10 see next chapter.

	Type		Chlorophyll-a					Q index				
	Type	ref	HG	GM	MP	PB	ref	HG	GM	MP	PB	
oligo	u-o	L01	1.2	2.2	6.2	13.3	27	6.74	6.53	6.19	5.91	5.63
	o	L02	1.5	2.9	7.4	15.4	31	6.62	6.35	6.07	5.82	5.55
	o	L03	1.5	2.9	7.4	15.4	31	6.62	6.35	6.07	5.82	5.55
m	o-m	L04	3.1	5.9	15.4	31	61	6.46	6.19	5.82	5.55	5.27
eu	e-h	L05	6.8	11.8	25	65	105	5.98	5.82	5.55	5.27	4.98
	h	L05a	6.8	11.8	25	65	105	5.98	5.82	5.55	5.27	4.98
	h	L06	6.8	11.8	25	65	105	5.98	5.82	5.55	5.27	4.98
	e-h	L07	6.8	10.7	26	52	107	5.98	5.82	5.55	5.27	4.98
	e-h	L08	6.8	10.7	26	52	107	5.98	5.82	5.55	5.27	4.98
-	-	L09	6.8	10.7	30	60	120	na	na	na	na	na
-	-	L10	6.8	10.7	30	60	120	na	na	na	na	na
m	o-m	L11a	3.7	7.1	17.0	34	68	6.35	6.07	5.76	5.48	5.21
	o-m	L11b	3.7	7.1	17.0	34	68	6.35	6.07	5.76	5.48	5.21
o	o	L11c	1.5	2.9	7.4	15.4	31	6.62	6.35	6.07	5.82	5.55
meso	o-m	L12	3.7	7.1	17.0	34	68	6.35	6.07	5.76	5.48	5.21
	o-m	L13	3.7	7.1	17.0	34	68	6.35	6.07	5.76	5.48	5.21
	m	L14	4.9	9.5	21	43	85	6.19	5.89	5.62	5.34	5.07
	m	L15	4.9	9.5	21	43	85	6.19	5.89	5.62	5.34	5.07
eu	e	L16	5.6	10.7	24	48	96	6.10	5.82	5.55	5.27	4.99
	e	L17	5.6	10.7	24	48	96	6.10	5.82	5.55	5.27	4.99

8.2 Hungarian lake phytoplankton index HLPI for freshwater lakes and reservoirs (incl. L7 and oligohaline L8)

The Hungarian lake phytoplankton index (HLPI) was developed by G. Borics and intercalibrated for the Lake Srebarna and comparable lakes in Hungary and Romania belonging to the IC type L-EC1 (Borics *et al.* 2018). It is based on three metrics: chlorophyll-a (Chl), composition metric (Q index) and the absolute abundance of Cyanobacteria as bloom metric (Figure 18).

For both Chl and Q index the ecological quality ratio (EQR) is calculated. To combine the two EQR the must be normalised (nEQR). The following algorithms are used to transform EQR values to nEQR values:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \text{EQR}_i & \text{nEQR}_i \\
 \geq \text{EQR}_{\text{H/G}} & (\text{EQR}_i - \text{EQR}_{\text{H/G}}) / (1 - \text{EQR}_{\text{H/G}}) * 0.2 + 0.8 \\
 & \text{if } \text{nEQR}_i > 1, \text{ then } \text{nEQR}_i \text{ is set to } 1 \\
 \text{EQR}_{\text{H/G}} > \text{EQR}_i \geq \text{EQR}_{\text{G/M}} & (\text{EQR}_i - \text{EQR}_{\text{G/M}}) / (\text{EQR}_{\text{H/G}} - \text{EQR}_{\text{G/M}}) * 0.2 + 0.6 \\
 \text{EQR}_{\text{G/M}} > \text{EQR}_i \geq \text{EQR}_{\text{M/P}} & (\text{EQR}_i - \text{EQR}_{\text{M/P}}) / (\text{EQR}_{\text{G/M}} - \text{EQR}_{\text{M/P}}) * 0.2 + 0.4 \\
 \text{EQR}_{\text{M/P}} > \text{EQR}_i \geq \text{EQR}_{\text{P/B}} & (\text{EQR}_i - \text{EQR}_{\text{P/B}}) / (\text{EQR}_{\text{M/P}} - \text{EQR}_{\text{P/B}}) * 0.2 + 0.2 \\
 < \text{EQR}_{\text{P/B}} & (\text{EQR}_i - \text{EQR}_{\text{min}}) / (\text{EQR}_{\text{P/B}} - \text{EQR}_{\text{min}}) * 0.2
 \end{array}$$

Each class includes the lower class boundary (e.g. $nEQR = 0.8 \rightarrow$ high status). Per definitionem, $nEQR$ values >1 are fixed at 1, while values <0 are fixed at 0.

The weighted arithmetic mean of the two $nEQR$ gives the HLPI.

$$HLPI = \frac{nEQR_Q + 2 \times nEQR_{chl}}{3}$$

HLPI: Hungarian lake phytoplankton index

$nEQR_Q$: normalized EQR of the composition metric (Q index)

$nEQR_{chl}$: normalized EQR of the biomass (Chlorophyll-a metric)

The WFD requires that the frequency and intensity of algal blooms are considered in phytoplankton-based quality assessment. Since the term water bloom is not clearly defined in the hydrobiological literature, several approaches such as evenness and relative or absolute abundance of cyanobacteria have been tested by Borics *et al.* (2018). Neither the evenness nor the relative abundance of cyanobacteria seemed to be applicable as bloom metric, while the absolute abundance of cyanobacteria turned out to be a promising predictor of algal blooms. The following threshold was defined:

- If cyanobacteria biomass is $\leq 8 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (respectively $\leq 4 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ for drinking water reservoirs), the value of the HLPI can directly be applied.
- If cyanobacteria biomass is $> 8 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (respectively $> 4 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ for drinking water reservoirs):
 - $HLPI > 0.6 \rightarrow$ the HLPI is reduced by 0.2
 - $HLPI \leq 0.6 \rightarrow$ no change of the HLPI

The threshold was defined from Chorus & Testai (2021) as alert level 1 to describe an enhanced risk of dominance of toxin producing cyanobacteria.

Figure 18. Phytoplankton metrics and their contributions in the Hungarian Lake Phytoplankton Index (HLPI).

The result of the classification of the monitoring sites in BG based on phytoplankton are summarised in the data annex (chapter 13.2).

9 Transitional waters belonging to L9, L10 and R16

The national types L9 and L10 as well as the river type R16 (which is the only river type where phytoplankton can be used to assess the ecological status) are transitional waters. The phytoplankton community in these systems significantly differ from those in freshwater lakes and the other two transitional types L7 and L8. However, the requirements for the classification method according to the WFD are the same. Several phytoplankton indicators must be used to evaluate the deviation from a designated undisturbed status: phytoplankton biomass, taxonomic composition and abundance, and the frequency and intensity of blooms.

For this project, different methods used in the literature were evaluated. A method where data from transitional waters from Bulgaria were included was presented by Lugoli *et al.* (2012). Among other parameters, it uses size classes of phytoplankton. The experts involved in this study were contacted by the project experts. According to their judgment, the method is not appropriate for regular monitoring as the microscopic work for the determination of the algal size classes is too time-consuming. Also Italy, which was involved in this study, does currently not apply this method.

The method described in Brito *et al.* (2012) is pragmatic but not fully compliant with the requirements of the WFD. It was developed for transitional waters in the Northeast Atlantic and includes only chlorophyll-a and bloom frequency, but does not consider the taxonomic composition. In addition, the Northeast Atlantic is rather different from the Black Sea and, hence, the class boundaries suggested by the authors are not uncritically applied to the estuaries in Bulgaria.

A method developed in the UK (Devlin *et al.* 2014) is a sophisticated and good method but requires a high effort of monitoring (monthly sampling), which goes beyond the current method and the financial resources available in Bulgaria. Therefore, the method cannot be applied in the routine monitoring.

Finally, the IC report on methods in Mediterranean countries, published three years ago by Ponis *et al.* (2018), provides the most promising method. It includes a description of the Multimetric Phytoplankton Index MPI, which is used in Italy, Greece and Croatia, while France and Spain (the other countries involved in this IC exercise) use national indices.

The MPI is based on four sampling dates (like in BG) and includes diversity and dominance indices, bloom frequency and chl-a. The following description is directly taken from the IC report:

The index has to be calculated using seasonal data for at least 1 year (preferably February, May, August and November) to reduce the effect of seasonality. Only organisms identifiable to species level (single indeterminate taxa, such as Navicula sp. 1, Cryptophyceae sp. 1, Taxa sp.1, can be included) by means of conventional inverted light microscope (cells size >2 µm) have to be used to calculate abundance (N) and hence Hulburt's dominance index, bloom frequency and Menhinick's diversity index. Multiple indeterminate taxa, such as genus spp., Cryptophyceae spp., flagellates, etc. have to be grouped under "multiple indeterminate taxa".

- *Hulburt's index δ_2*

The first metric is species dominance, calculated using Hulburt's index (Hulburt 1963):

$$\delta_2 = \frac{100 \cdot (n_1 + n_2)}{N}$$

where n_1 = abundance of the dominant species; n_2 = abundance of the second most abundant species; and N = abundance of identified taxa

In order to relate Hulbert's index to water quality, the "100 – δ_2 " value has to be used.

- Bloom frequency F

Bloom frequency is defined as the number of times (i.e. the number of monthly samples) in which the abundance of a single species exceeded 50% of abundance (N) at each sampling site. The numerical value of this second metric was termed "100 – Bloom Frequency" ($100 - F$).

- Menhinick's index D

Menhinick's index is the third metric:

$$D = S/\sqrt{N}$$

where S = number of species and N = abundance of identified taxa.

To reduce the error caused by deletion of multiple indeterminate taxa, a correction factor was introduced. This factor was calculated as the ratio of the total determinate taxa to the original total abundance (determinate + indeterminate taxa). For each sample Menhinick's index (D) was multiplied by the correction factor.

- Chlorophyll-a concentration $Chl-a$

The $Chl-a$ data have to be \log_{10} -transformed and outliers (values outside the range |average \pm 2.5 * std. dev.|) removed in order to create a more robust dataset. Considering the new dataset, average concentrations were calculated for each sampling site and the antilogs were then calculated.

Reference values were used to determine the Ecological Quality Ratio (EQR) for each metric as a whole-year average, on a scale between 0 and 1.

For $100 - \delta_2$, $100 - F$ and Menhinick's index (D):

$$EQR = \text{Observed values} / \text{Reference value}$$

For Chlorophyll-a concentrations:

$$EQR = \text{Reference value} / \text{Observed values}$$

The Multimetric Phytoplankton Index (MPI) was calculated by averaging the 4 EQRs at each site:

$$MPI = \text{mean} (EQR(100-\delta_2); EQR(100-F); EQR(D); EQR(Chl a)).$$

In estuaries of Croatia, the definition of reference values and setting of class boundaries was carried out as follows:

The highest values for Hulburt's index ($100 - \delta_2$), bloom frequency ($100 - F$) and Menhinick index with environmental conditions ($LUSI^2$ and nutrient concentrations) on sites where they were obtained are taken into consideration to select the reference values by expert judgment. The 30th percentile of averaged and antilogged chlorophyll a data is taken as the reference value for this metric ... due to different hydrodynamic conditions of studied estuaries and different natural features of river basins.

According to the Water Framework Directive (WFD), the index range was equally divided into 5 ecological status classes (H/G = 0.8, G/M = 0.6 etc.).

Additional reference values are provided for lagoons in Italy and Greece. The original values developed for these countries, however, cannot be directly applied to Bulgaria. The relative approach as applied in Croatia seems more reasonable, although it requires a data set which is sufficiently high and covers a large pressure gradient. Otherwise, the highest value cannot be expected to represent the reference value and the percentile calculation is questionable. A thorough look at the GIG report revealed, however, that also there a considerable amount of expert judgment was used and necessary to define reference values and set class boundaries.

Based on our data, but taking into account the outcome of the Med-GIG on transitional waters (Ponis *et al.* 2018), we propose the following reference values:

Hulburt's index	$100 - \delta$	60	based on 58 as maximum value in our data set (n=16)
Bloom frequency	$100 - F \cdot 100$	100	assuming that it is possible under reference conditions that, at least in some years, no blooms occur at all
Menhinick's index	D	0.030	by expert judgment, taking into account the regression in Figure 16
Chl-a	for L9, L10	6.8	based on the regression with TP, cf Table 58
	for R16	5.0	by expert judgment

The class boundaries were derived for Hulburt, bloom frequency and Menhinick's index by equally dividing the range from reference value to 0 into 5 intervals. For Chlorophyll-a, the class boundaries in L9 and L10 were already defined above (Table 58). For the transitional rivers, an increase from one class to another by a factor of about 2 (like for lakes) was assumed to sufficiently reflect the exponential increase along the trophic gradient and is suggested for boundary setting. Reference values and class boundaries for the four metrics are summarized in Table 59.

² Land use index

Table 59. Reference values and class boundaries for the 4 metrics used for the calculation of the MPI in transitional waters of type L9, L10 and R16.

Metric	Abbreviation	Type	ref	HG	GM	MP	PB
Hulburt's index δ	$100 - \delta$	L9, L10, R16	60	48	36	24	12
Bloom frequency F	$100 - F * 100$	L9, L10, R16	100	80	60	40	20
Menhinick's index	D	L9, L10, R16	0.03	0.024	0.018	0.012	0.006
Chlorophyll-a	Chl-a ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	L9, L10	6.8	10.7	30	60	120
		R16	5.0	10	20	40	80

The EQR values for Hulburt, bloom frequency and Minhinick's index are 0.8 for H/G, 0.6 for G/M, 0.4 for M/P and 0.2 for P/B. hence, they already correspond to normalised EQR. For the Chlorophyll-a, the EQR must be normalised as described above in chapter 8.2 before combining them with the EQR of the other metrics.

Table 60. Reference values and class boundaries of EQR and normalised EQR for the 4 metrics used for the calculation of the MPI in transitional waters of type L9, L10 and R16.

Metric	Abbreviation	Type		ref	HG	GM	MP	PB
Hulburt's index δ	$100 - \delta$	L9, L10, R16	EQR = nEQR	1.0	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.2
Bloom frequency F	$100 - F * 100$	L9, L10, R16	EQR = nEQR	1.0	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.2
Menhinick's index	D	L9, L10, R16	EQR = nEQR	1.0	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.2
Chlorophyll-a	Chl-a ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	L9, L10	EQR	1.0	0.6355	0.2267	0.1133	0.0567
			nEQR	1.0	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.2
		R16	EQR	1.0	0.5	0.25	0.125	0.083
			nEQR	1.0	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.2

When combining the four nEQR in the calculation of the MPI, also this multimetric index has normalised class boundaries at equal distances (H/G 0.8, G/M 0.6 etc.).

The ecological characteristics at high and good status are described as follows:

Phytoplanktonic communities representative of reference conditions sites are characterised by an equilibrium of species with consequent high biodiversity, low Chlorophyll and nutrient loading and absence of dominance phenomena. At good status, the effect of eutrophication and the impact of nutrient status starts to negatively affect the community. Some isolated dominance phenomena can take place, reduction of diversity of the community which is still differentiated. The metrics composing the MPI are strictly related to these phenomena.

Based on literature recherche and after evaluation of different methods, we recommend adopting the index MPI used in the IC exercise for the BG national types L9, L10 and R16.

10 Ecological potential

In most cases, physical alterations of a lake have little or no measurable effect on the phytoplankton. Therefore, ecological status and ecological potential is the same for this BQE. This is in line with the current national document on EP determination and supported by the fact that the ecological *status* (and not potential) of Mediterranean reservoirs was successfully intercalibrated in the first IC phase (Pahissa *et al.* 2015).

In Bulgaria, different trophic and chemical conditions can be expected for one lake type only. Two L10 lakes are currently used as salinas and hence hyperhaline. In the general document on HMWB, the installation of the separate protected zone within these lakes was proposed as a measure without significant adverse effect on the use. This would have a clear effect on salinity and in consequence on the BQE phytoplankton. The current data and the low number of HMWB sites belonging to this type does not allow defining EP with sufficient confidence. Therefore, we recommend following the *mitigation measures approach* for the classification of HMWB of type 10 using phytoplankton and use the method for ES assessment as described in the previous section. If the mitigation measure can be implemented, future monitoring data can be used to describe the changes in the phytoplankton community and develop a salinity-dependent assessment method for this BQE beyond the trophic classification.

11 Conclusion

This Annex summarises the results of comprehensive analyses on nutrients and phytoplankton in Bulgarian lakes/reservoirs as well as the transitional river type R16. It presents reference values and class boundaries for nutrients (TP, TN) for all national lake types and the river type R16. The biological method for lakes/reservoirs recommended by the expert team is the HLPI, which is a multimetric index including chlorophyll-a and the Q index. For the transitional lakes L9 and L10 and for the transitional river type R16, we recommend applying the MPI, a multimetric index based on diversity indices, bloom frequency and chlorophyll-a, which was used in the IC exercise on transitional water bodies in the Mediterranean region and is the national method in Italy, Greece and Croatia.

The ecological potential is not relevant for the BQE phytoplankton except for the HMWB belonging to L10. However, at present it is not possible to follow the reference approach (acc. to the CIS Guidance No. 37) and define class boundaries with sufficient confidence. We rather recommend following the mitigation measures (acc. to the CIS Guidance No. 37) as described in the General Document on EP Definition (= Annex 1 of the Final Report).

The methods developed are compliant with the WFD and recommended to be included in an amendment of the national Ordinance H-4 for the general physical-chemical quality element nutrients (with the parameters total phosphorus and total nitrogen) and the BQE phytoplankton.

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13 Data annex

13.1 Monitoring sites

Cells with grey shading highlight sites where the type differs from the overall SWB type. Blue shading highlight the R16 transitional river sites.

SWB	Cat	MonitringSiteCode	SiteName	Type	Type SWB	Altitude	Altid. class	Area km ²	Area class	Vol Mio m ³	Z _{max} m	Z _{avg} m
BG1DJ345L1014	HMWB	BG1DJ09991MS1031	Onogur Reservoir	L16	L16	85	<200	0.6	0.5-1 km ²			
BG1IS500L1008	HMWB	BG1IS05993MS051	Pancharevo Reservoir	L12	L12	597	500-800	0.7	0.5-1 km ²	6.5		9.1
BG1IS200L1021	HMWB	BG1IS22919MS031	Bebresh Reservoir	L02	L02	492	200-500	0.9	0.5-1 km ²			
BG1IS600L1014	HMWB	BG1IS69539MS041	Ognyanovo Reservoir	L02	L02	610	500-800	3.3	1-10 km ²	31.6		9.7
BG1IS700L1005	HMWB	BG1IS77799MS061	Iskar Reservoir	L11a	L11	814	800-1800	27.6	10-100 km ²	655.3		23.7
BG1IS900L1002	HMWB	BG1IS94733MS071	Beli Iskar Reservoir	L01	L01	1879	>1800	0.8	0.5-1 km ²	15.1		19.2
BG1NV200R1001	natural	BG1L04NVHM001_EEA	Dragoman Marsh	L04	R02	702	500-800				1	
BG1OG700L1004	HMWB	BG1L14OGHM004_EEA	Ogosta Reservoir - tail	L14	L14	189	<200	17.3	10-100 km ²	506.0		29.3
BG1VT300L1012	HMWB	BG1L14VTHM002_EEA	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir - tail	L14	L14	171	<200	5.3	1-10 km ²	130.0		24.4
BG1OG700L1004	HMWB	BG1OG00739MS031	Ogosta Reservoir	L14	L14	189	<200	17.3	10-100 km ²	506.0		29.3
BG1OG700L1016	AWB	BG1OG00744MS041	Srechenska Bara Reservoir	L12	L16	450	200-500	0.8	0.5-1 km ²	15.5		19.6
BG1RL200L1006	HMWB	BG1RL23419MS041	Kavatsite Reservoir	L12	L12	206	200-500	0.6	0.5-1 km ²			
BG1RL900L1009	HMWB	BG1RL93979MS051	Beli Lom Reservoir	L12	L12	279	200-500	2.8	1-10 km ²	25.5		9.1
BG1VT300L1010	HMWB	BG1VT00032MS041	Telish Reservoir	L12	L16	216	200-500	1.3	1-10 km ²			
BG1VT300L1012	HMWB	BG1VT00325MS031	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir	L14	L14	171	<200	5.3	1-10 km ²	130.0		24.4
BG1VT800L1004	HMWB	BG1VT00891MS051	Sopot Reservoir	L12	L12	365	200-500	3.4	1-10 km ²	60.9		17.9
BG1WO800L021	AWB	BG1WO00812MS061	Kovachitsa Reservoir	L16	L16	111	<200	1.0	1-10 km ²			
BG1WO800L1020	HMWB	BG1WO00814MS071	Rasovo Reservoir	L16	L16	133	<200	0.4	<0.5 km ²			
BG1WO300L018	HMWB	BG1WO03496MS031	Rabisha Reservoir	L04	L04	294	200-500	2.4	1-10 km ²	43.2		18.3
BG1WO200L1003	HMWB	BG1WO29791MS011	Kula Reservoir	L12	L12	202	200-500	1.2	1-10 km ²	20.3		16.4
BG1WO300L1006	HMWB	BG1WO32939MS021	Poletkovtsi Reservoir	L12	L12	201	200-500	0.5	<0.5 km ²			
BG1YN400L1005	HMWB	BG1YN04471MS031	Krapets Reservoir	L12	L12	407	200-500	1.3	1-10 km ²			
BG1YN600L1019	HMWB	BG1YN06295MS180	Yovkovtsi Reservoir-tail	L02	L02	336	200-500	7.7	1-10 km ²	92.2		12.0
BG1YN600L1024	HMWB	BG1YN06496MS061	Yastrebino Reservoir	L12	L12	337	200-500	5.4	1-10 km ²	62.3		11.5
BG1YN400L1009	HMWB	BG1YN43199MS021	Al. Stamboliyski Reservoir	L14	L11	186	<200	9.8	1-10 km ²	205.6		21.0
BG1YN600L1019	HMWB	BG1YN62953MS041	Yovkovtsi Reservoir-wall	L02	L02	336	200-500	7.7	1-10 km ²	92.2		12.0
BG1YN900L1014	HMWB	BG1YN92233MS051	Hristo Smirnenski Reservoir	L02	L02	533	500-800	1.0	0.5-1 km ²	27.7		28.5
BG2DO700L017	natural	BG2DO10000MS006	Lake Durankulashko	L07	L07	0	<200	2.5	1-10 km ²			
BG2DO700L018	natural	BG2DO10000MS007	Lake Shabla	L07	L07	4	<200	2.7	1-10 km ²			
BG2DO700L018	natural	BG2DO10000MS482	Lake Ezeretsko	L07	L07	4	<200	2.7	1-10 km ²			

SWB	Cat	MonitringSiteCode	SiteName	Type	Type SWB	Altitude	Altid. class	Area km ²	Area class	Vol Mio m ³	Z _{max} m	Z _{avg} m
BG2DO700L018	natural	BG2DO10000MS483	Lake Ezeretsko	L07	L07	4	<200	2.7	1-10 km ²			
BG2IU600L018	natural	BG2IU00061MS258	Dyavolsko Marsh	L08	L08	3	<200	0.1	<0.5 km ²			
BG2IU800R1115	natural	BG2IU00081MS254	Lisovo Dere River (Izgrevska Dere) - estuary, Tsarevo	R16	R16	5	<200					
BG2IU400L011	HMWB	BG2IU04919MS007	Yasna polyana Reservoir	L16	L12	92	<200	2.1	1-10 km ²	32.3		15.7
BG2IU200R1005	natural	BG2IU07211MS404	Ropotamo River - before estuary, bridge on E 87	R16	R16	10	<200					
BG2IU200L017	natural	BG2IU10000MS004	Lake Alepu, from the shore	L08	L08	10	<200	1.1	1-10 km ²			
BG2IU200L007	natural	BG2IU20000MS257	lake Stamopolu	L08	L08	3	<200	0.04	<0.5 km ²			
BG2IU200R1005	natural	BG2IU200L005RP15	Veliov vir Lake	L05a	R16	11	<200		<0.5 km ²			
BG2IU200L019	natural	BG2IU200L019RP18	Arkutino Lake	L05a	L05a	3	<200	0.3	<0.5 km ²			
BG2IU200R1005	natural	BG2IU200R005RP14	Ropotamo River in MR "Veliov Vir"	R16	R16	13	<200					
BG2IU600R1013	natural	BG2IU6915MS002	Karaagach River - estuary	R16	R16	5	<200					
BG2KA200L006	HMWB	BG2KA00233MS037	Eleshnitsa Reservoir	L16	L12	58	<200	0.9	0.5-1 km ²			
BG2KA800L029	HMWB	BG2KA00863MS036	Saedinenie Reservoir	L16	L12	175	<200	2.5	1-10 km ²	12.8		5.2
BG2KA900L021	HMWB	BG2KA00961MS023	Ticha Reservoir	L14	L11	184	<200	18.4	10-100 km ²	311.8		17.0
BG2KA400L008	HMWB	BG2KA04195MS008	Tsonevo Reservoir	L14	L11	59	<200	15.6	10-100 km ²			
BG2KA800L027	HMWB	BG2KA08471MS261	Fisek Reservoir	L16	L12	174	<200	1.2	1-10 km ²			
BG2KA800L032	AWB	BG2KA08962MS262	Polyanitsa Reservoir	L12	L12	238	200-500	0.7	0.5-1 km ²			
BG2KA400L044	AWB	BG2KA47379MS488	Skala 1 Reservoir	L04	L04	470	200-500	0.7	0.5-1 km ²		11	
BG2KA400L024	HMWB	BG2KA47399MS020	Kamchia Reservoir	L11a	L11	256	200-500	9.6	1-10 km ²	233.6		24.2
BG2KA900L036	HMWB	BG2KA90000MS260	Cherkonva Reservoir	L12	L12	281	200-500	0.6	0.5-1 km ²			
BG2SE900L028	HMWB	BG2L10SETR003_EEA	Lake Pomorie - west	L10	L10	0	<200	6.0	1-10 km ²			
BG2SE900L027	HMWB	BG2L10SETR004_EEA	Lake Atanasovsko - south	L10	L10	0	<200	9.7	1-10 km ²			
BG2MA100L001	HMWB	BG2MA00019MS009	lake Mandra - east	L09	L09	8	<200	1.9	1-10 km ²			
BG2MA100L001	HMWB	BG2MA00611MS008	lake Mandra -west	L09	L09	8	<200	1.9	1-10 km ²			
BG2MA600L017	HMWB	BG2MA06945MS265	Kartelka Reservoir	L16	L16	105	<200	0.5	0.5-1 km ²			
BG2MA107L002	HMWB	BG2MA10000MS006	dam Mandra	L07	L07	29	<200	33.0	10-100 km ²			
BG2MA107L002	HMWB	BG2MA10000MS007	dam Mandra - iztok	L07	L07	29	<200	33.0	10-100 km ²			
BG2MA600L016	HMWB	BG2MA64911MS264	Krushovo Reservoir	L16	L16	105	<200	1.7	1-10 km ²			
BG2PR100L002	HMWB	BG2PR00155MS012	Channel between Beloslavsko Lake and Varna Lake (Channel 2)	L09	L09	0	<200	1.5	1-10 km ²			
BG2PR100L001	HMWB	BG2PR00155MS013	Varna Lake - west	L09	L09	1	<200	15.7	10-100 km ²			
BG2PR100L001	HMWB	BG2PR00155MS014	Varna Lake - northwest	L09	L09	1	<200	15.7	10-100 km ²			
BG2PR100L001	HMWB	BG2PR00155MS015	Varna Lake - Center	L09	L09	1	<200	15.7	10-100 km ²			
BG2PR100L001	HMWB	BG2PR00155MS016	Varna Lake - East	L09	L09	1	<200	15.7	10-100 km ²			

Annex 2: Ecological Status Classification System – Phytoplankton

SWB	Cat	MonitringSiteCode	SiteName	Type	Type SWB	Altitude	Altid. class	Area km ²	Area class	Vol Mio m ³	Z _{max} m	Z _{avg} m
BG2PR900L019	HMWB	BG2PR00155MS017	Old Channel	L09	L09	3	<200	0.1	<0.5 km ²			
BG2PR900L020	AWB	BG2PR00155MS018	New Channel (Channel 1)	L09	L09	4	<200	0.3	<0.5 km ²			
BG2PR100L003	HMWB	BG2PR00191MS010	Beloslavsko Lake - east	L09	L09	1	<200	7.3	1-10 km ²			
BG2PR100L003	HMWB	BG2PR01931MS011	Beloslavsko Lake - west	L09	L09	1	<200	7.3	1-10 km ²			
BG2RE200R1201	natural	BG2RE00219MS497	Silistar River - before inflow into Black Sea (estuary)	R16	R16	10	<200					
BG2RE200R1101	natural	BG2RE92529MS496	Butamiyata River- estuary	R16	R16	1	<200					
BG2SE200R1001	natural	BG2SE00219MS228	Fandakliyska River - estuary	R16	R11	1	<200					
BG2SE600L016	HMWB	BG2SE00691MS029	Poroy Reservoir	L16	L16	39	<200	1.8	1-10 km ²	45.2		25.1
BG2SE800L018	HMWB	BG2SE08331MS028	Aheloy Reservoir	L16	L16	149	<200	0.7	0.5-1 km ²	12.7		18.8
BG2SE800R020	HMWB	BG2SE81MS008	Aheloy River - Camping Aheloy	R16	R16	3	<200					
BG2SE900L028	HMWB	BG2SE90000MS020	Lake Pomorie - south	L10	L10	0	<200	6.0	1-10 km ²			
BG2SE900L027	HMWB	BG2SE90000MS021	Lake Atanasovsko - north	L10	L10	0	<200	9.7	1-10 km ²			
BG2SE900L037	HMWB	BG2SE90000MS022	Burgas Lake- west	L08	L08	1	<200	25.4	10-100 km ²			
BG2SE900L037	HMWB	BG2SE90000MS023	Burgas Lake- center	L08	L08	1	<200	25.4	10-100 km ²			
BG2SE900L037	HMWB	BG2SE90000MS024	Burgas Lake - east	L08	L08	1	<200	25.4	10-100 km ²			
BG2SE900L032	HMWB	BG2SE98935MS263	Troyanovo Reservoir	L16	L16	90	<200	1.0	0.5-1 km ²			
BG2VE106R1801	natural	BG2VE111MS001	Veleka River – Sinemorets village	R16	R16	4	<200					
BG3AR350L010	HMWB	BG3AR00031MS0070	Studen kladenets Reservoir-wall	L11b	L11	218	200-500	31.1	10-100 km ²	387.8	63.0	12.5
BG3AR570L021	HMWB	BG3AR00055MS0200	Kardzhali Reservoir	L11b	L11	307	200-500	16.4	10-100 km ²	497.2	96.0	30.3
BG3AR600L025	HMWB	BG3AR00067MS0210	Borovitsa Reservoir	L13	L13	482	200-500	1.0	1-10 km ²	27.3	64.0	27.1
BG3AR800L041	natural	BG3AR00086MS0290	Smolianski Lakes (Trevisto Lake)	L03	L03	1525	800-1800	0.1	<0.5 km ²			
BG3AR100L004	HMWB	BG3AR00133MS0020	Ivaylovgrad Reservoir - wall	L15	L11	120	<200	18.3	10-100 km ²	156.7	62.0	8.6
BG3MA350R211	natural	BG3L06MANA002_EEA	Krairechna Murtvitsa Lake near v. Popovitsa	L06	R12	135	<200					
BG3MA350R212	natural	BG3L06MANA003_EEA	Protected Area "Zlato pole"(old meander of Maritsa River)	L06	R12	87	<200					
BG3MA200L210	HMWB	BG3MA00225MS0120	Ovcharitsa Reservoir	L15	L15	134	<200	9.4	1-10 km ²	45.8	17.3	4.9
BG3MA300L045	HMWB	BG3MA00324MS1239	Garvanovo Reservoir	L13	L15	212	200-500	2.8	1-10 km ²	25.0		9.0
BG3MA300L054	HMWB	BG3MA00338MS7269	Chirpan Reservoir	L17	L17	138	<200	0.4	<0.5 km ²	1.6	8.8	3.8
BG3MA300L058	HMWB	BG3MA00344MS0296	Lenovo Reservoir	L13	L17	335	200-500	0.4	<0.5 km ²	6.1		16.5
BG3MA300L061	HMWB	BG3MA00347MS0280	Mechka Reservoir	L13	L17	324	200-500	0.3	<0.5 km ²	6.8	30.0	25.2
BG3MA400L086	HMWB	BG3MA00445MS0430	Sinjata reka Reservoir	L13	L17	301	200-500	0.4	<0.5 km ²	2.4	10.4	5.3
BG3MA500L119	HMWB	BG3MA00545MS0640	Piasachnik Reservoir	L11b	L15	283	200-500	12.5	10-100 km ²	206.5	39.1	16.5
BG3MA600L133	HMWB	BG3MA00631MS0720	Vacha Reservoir	L13	L13	541	500-800	4.9	1-10 km ²	226.1	140.3	46.2
BG3MA200L019	AWB	BG3MA02191MS0116	Rozov Kladenets Reservoir	L15	L15	102	<200	5.5	1-10 km ²	20.4	10.1	3.7

SWB	Cat	MonitringSiteCode	SiteName	Type	Type SWB	Altitude	Altid. class	Area km ²	Area class	Vol Mio m ³	Z _{max} m	Z _{avg} m
BG3MA300L041	HMWB	BG3MA03143MS1226	Byalo Pole Reservoir	L17	L17	140	<200	1.1	1-10 km ²	1.0	5.5	1.0
BG3MA300L068	AWB	BG3MA03742MS0322	General Nikolaevo Reservoir-1	L17	L17	200	<200	0.8	0.5-1 km ²	3.9	10.5	4.9
BG3MA300L074	HMWB	BG3MA03929MS0371	Sushitsa Reservoir	L13	L17	434	200-500	0.4	<0.5 km ²	4.6	36.0	11.1
BG3MA400L213	HMWB	BG3MA04623MS0445	Domlyan Reservoir	L13	L13	344	200-500	1.5	1-10 km ²	26.1	39.0	17.5
BG3MA400L092	HMWB	BG3MA04629MS0451	Svezhen Reservoir	L13	L13	810	800-1800	0.02	<0.5 km ²			
BG3MA600L138	HMWB	BG3MA06481MS0740	Golyam Beglik Reservoir	L03	L03	1531	800-1800	4.0	1-10 km ²	86.1		21.3
BG3MA800L160	HMWB	BG3MA08191MS1120	Topolnitsa Reservoir-wall	L13	L13	376	200-500	7.2	1-10 km ²	137.1	74.0	19.1
BG3MA900L205	HMWB	BG3MA09549MS1510	Belmeken Reservoir	L03	L03	1950	>1800	3.8	1-10 km ²	149.5		38.9
BG3MA100L012	HMWB	BG3MA18739MS0071	Trakiets Reservoir	L13	L15	245	200-500	4.7	1-10 km ²	114.0	40.0	24.5
BG3MA900L192	HMWB	BG3MA92259MS1410	Batak Reservoir	L03	L03	1103	800-1800	21.0	10-100 km ²	310.3		14.8
BG3TU700L036	HMWB	BG3TU00077MS0220	Zhrebchevo Reservoir-wall	L11b	L11	260	200-500	19.1	10-100 km ²	400.0	47.8	21.0
BG3TU600L023	HMWB	BG3TU00656MS0110	Tsanko Tserkovski Reservoir	L17	L17	150	<200	1.7	1-10 km ²	6.5	4.0	3.8
BG3TU700L030	HMWB	BG3TU00725MS0180	Asenovets Reservoir	L13	L13	414	200-500	1.1	1-10 km ²	28.2	63.0	25.7
BG3TU900L047	HMWB	BG3TU00955MS0340	Koprinka Reservoir	L11b	L11	381	200-500	11.4	10-100 km ²	142.2	43.0	12.5
BG3TU500L013	HMWB	BG3TU05239MS0040	Malko Sharkovo Reservoir	L13	L13	235	200-500	2.9	1-10 km ²	45.0	37.0	15.5
BG4ME500R107	HMWB	BG4L06MENA001_EEA	Riparian Wetlands near Gotse Delchev (Mesta river)	L06	R05	502	500-800					
BG4ME700L1009	natural	BG4ME0000NMS003	Bezbog Lake	L01	L01	2248	>1800					
BG4DO900L117	HMWB	BG4ME00292MS902	Dospat Reservoir-tail	L11c	L11	1199	800-1800	19.6	10-100 km ²	449.2		22.9
BG4DO900L117	HMWB	BG4ME00292MS903	Dospat Reservoir-sadki	L11c	L11	1199	800-1800	19.6	10-100 km ²	449.2		22.9
BG4DO900L117	HMWB	BG4ME00292MS905	Dospat Reservoir-wall	L11c	L11	1199	800-1800	19.6	10-100 km ²	449.2		22.9
BG4DO600L119	HMWB	BG4ME02661MS914	Shiroka Polyana Reservoir - village zone	L03	L03	1525	800-1800	4.0	1-10 km ²			
BG4DO600L119	HMWB	BG4ME02661MS915	Shiroka Polyana Reservoir	L03	L03	1525	800-1800	4.0	1-10 km ²			
BG4ME700L1009	natural	BG4ME47382MS815	Kremensko ezero	L01	L01	2310	>1800					
BG4ST500L1006	HMWB	BG4ST0000NMS001	Stoikovtsi Reservoir	L13	L13	628	500-800	2.8	1-10 km ²			
BG4ST900L1012	HMWB	BG4ST00691MS805	Choklyovo blato	L04	L04	874	800-1800	0.8	0.5-1 km ²		3	
BG4ST900L1010	HMWB	BG4ST06939MS915	Pchelina Reservoir	L13	L13	620	500-800	5.7	1-10 km ²	54.2		9.5
BG4ST900L1008	HMWB	BG4ST06963MS945	Dolna Dikanya Reservoir	L13	L13	708	500-800	0.7	0.5-1 km ²			
BG4ST900L1001	HMWB	BG4ST06992MS905	Studena Reservoir	L03	L03	846	800-1800	1.6	1-10 km ²	25.2		15.4
BG4ST500L1010	natural	BG4ST65349MS825	Gergiisko Lake	L01	L01	2346	>1800					
BG4ST600L1007	natural	BG4ST65891MS815	Chernoto Lake	L01	L01	2367	>1800					

13.2 Classification results

Freshwater and oligo-/mesohaline lakes and reservoirs

MonitoringSiteCode	SiteName	Type	Year	TN mg/L	TP mg/L	BV mm ³ /L	Chl µg/L	Q	Cyan mm ³ /L	nEQR Chl	nEQR Q	HLPI	ES
BG1IS94733MS071	Beli Iskar Reservoir	L01	2020	0.145	0.010	0.8	2.1 7.6	7.6	0.0	0.81	1.00	0.87	H
BG4ME0000NMS003	Bezbog Lake	L01	2020	0.660	0.010	2.0	5.4 6.8	6.8	0.0	0.62	1.00	0.74	G
BG4ST65891MS815	Chernoto Lake	L01	2020	0.163	0.010	0.2	2.7 7.9	7.9	0.0	0.75	1.00	0.83	H
BG4ST65349MS825	Gergiisko Lake	L01	2020	0.120	0.010	1.4	7.6 7.0	7.0	0.0	0.53	1.00	0.69	G
BG4ME47382MS815	Kremensko ezero	L01	2020	0.515	0.010	0.9	2.2 6.9	6.9	0.0	0.80	1.00	0.87	H
BG1IS22919MS031	Bebresh Reservoir	L02	2020	0.163	0.010	1.1	2.1 8.1	8.1	0.0	0.89	1.00	0.93	H
BG1YN92233MS051	Hristo Smirnenski Reservoir	L02	2020	0.223	0.010	0.8	2.1 8.1	8.1	0.0	0.88	1.00	0.92	H
BG1IS69539MS041	Ognyanovo Reservoir	L02	2020	0.263	0.010	3.0	5.7 7.4	7.4	0.2	0.64	1.00	0.76	G
BG1YN06295MS180	Yovkovtsi Reservoir-tail	L02	2020	0.460	0.016	1.9	4.0 6.0	6.0	0.0	0.71	0.73	0.72	G
BG1YN62953MS041	Yovkovtsi Reservoir-wall	L02	2020	0.463	0.010	0.7	2.3 5.6	5.6	0.0	0.85	0.53	0.74	G
BG3MA92259MS1410	Batak Reservoir	L03	2020	0.355	0.010	4.6	6.7 4.2	4.2	3.8	0.61	0.17	0.47	M
BG3MA09549MS1510	Belmeken Reservoir	L03	2020	0.218	0.010	1.0	2.1 7.0	7.0	0.0	0.87	1.00	0.92	H
BG3MA06481MS0740	Golyam Beglik Reservoir	L03	2020	0.148	0.010	2.2	3.9 7.0	7.0	0.0	0.71	1.00	0.81	H
BG4ME02661MS915	Shiroka Polyana Reservoir	L03	2020	0.165	0.010	1.8	13.1 7.1	7.1	0.1	0.43	1.00	0.62	G
BG4ME02661MS914	Shiroka Polyana Reservoir - village zone	L03	2020	0.100	0.010	1.4	11.0 7.3	7.3	0.0	0.47	1.00	0.65	G
BG3AR00086MS0290	Smolianski Lakes (Trevisto Lake)	L03	2020	0.660	0.010	6.6	27.9 5.3	5.3	0.0	0.22	0.38	0.27	P
BG4ST00691MS805	Choklyovo blato	L04	2020	1.573	0.018	3.0	6.8 5.1	5.1	1.1	0.76	0.51	0.67	G
BG1L04NVHM001_EEA	Dragoman Marsh	L04	2020	1.715	1.053	2.1	23.4 6.6	6.6	0.5	0.46	1.00	0.64	G
BG1WO03496MS031	Rabisha Reservoir	L04	2020	0.483	0.010	0.5	3.3 5.9	5.9	0.0	0.98	0.80	0.92	H
BG2KA47379MS488	Skala 1 Reservoir	L04	2020	2.208	0.581	33.3	87.6 3.1	3.1	27.3	0.14	0.14	0.14	B
BG2IU200L019RP18	Arkutino Lake	L05a	2020	4.110	0.910	20.3	238.9 5.7	5.7	0.1	0.09	1.00	0.39	P
BG2IU200L005RP15	Veliiov vir Lake	L05a	2020	1.313	0.106	8.1	81.8 6.9	6.9	0.2	0.29	1.00	0.53	M
BG3L06MANA002_EEA	Krairechna Murtvitsa Lake near v. Popovitsa	L06	2020	9.660	0.656	134.3	148.1 5.9	5.9	67.7	0.14	1.00	0.43	M
BG3L06MANA003_EEA	"Zlato pole"(old meander of Maritsa River)	L06	2020	1.930	0.091	23.5	103.4 3.0	3.0	18.0	0.21	0.15	0.19	B
BG4L06MENA001_EEA	Riparian Wetlands	L06	2020	0.286	0.010	4.4	13.1 6.4	6.4	0.1	0.76	1.00	0.84	H
BG2MA10000MS007	dam Mandra - iztok	L07	2020	1.103	0.130	38.4	81.8 4.5	4.5	15.6	0.26	0.40	0.31	P
BG2DO10000MS483	Lake Ezeretsko	L07	2020	3.633	0.016	1.6	8.8 5.0	5.0	0.5	0.87	0.65	0.80	G

MonitoringSiteCode	SiteName	Type	Year	TN mg/L	TP mg/L	BV mm ³ /L	Chl µg/L	Q	Cyan mm ³ /L	nEQR Chl	nEQR Q	HLPI	ES
BG2DO10000MS007	Lake Shabla	L07	2020	1.930	0.022	1.4	8.4	5.8	0.6	0.90	1.00	0.93	H
BG2SE90000MS024	Burgas Lake - east	L08	2020	5.228	0.170	64.3	154.1	2.9	36.6	0.14	0.14	0.14	B
BG2SE90000MS022	Burgas Lake- west	L08	2020	4.895	0.459	66.3	171.0	3.7	32.4	0.12	0.19	0.14	B
BG2IU00061MS258	Dyavolsko Marsh	L08	2020	1.045	0.100	10.1	64.2	6.7	0.4	0.33	1.00	0.55	M
BG2IU10000MS004	Lake Alepu, from the shore	L08	2020	2.505	0.060	18.8	65.9	6.4	0.4	0.32	1.00	0.54	M
BG2IU20000MS257	lake Stamopolu	L08	2020	2.713	0.660	8.1	149.4	6.0	0.3	0.14	1.00	0.43	M
BG2KA47399MS020	Kamchia Reservoir	L11a	2020	0.643	0.013	1.4	3.4	6.3	0.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	H
BG3MA00545MS0640	Piasachnik Reservoir	L11b	2020	1.123	0.129	40.1	54.9	6.4	2.1	0.25	1.00	0.50	M
BG3TU00077MS0220	Zhrebchevo Reservoir-wall	L11b	2020	na	na	2.9	11.5	5.6	1.6	0.67	0.77	0.70	G
BG4ME00292MS905	Dospat Reservoir-wall	L11c	2020	na	na	0.9	3.3	6.5	0.0	0.76	0.95	0.82	H
BG1YN04471MS031	Krapets Reservoir	L12	2020	0.388	0.012	1.0	7.8	6.5	0.1	0.77	1.00	0.85	H
BG1VT00891MS051	Sopot Reservoir	L12	2020	0.183	0.010	0.3	4.3	7.4	0.0	0.94	1.00	0.96	H
BG1OG00744MS041	Srechenska Bara Reservoir	L12	2020	0.618	0.010	0.3	2.2	3.7	0.0	1.00	0.17	0.72	G
BG1VT00032MS041	Telish Reservoir	L12	2020	0.258	0.018	2.8	21.0	6.3	0.3	0.52	1.00	0.68	G
BG1YN06496MS061	Yastrebino Reservoir	L12	2020	0.853	0.010	8.5	23.9	4.8	3.7	0.48	0.38	0.45	P
BG4ST06963MS945	Dolna Dikanya Reservoir	L13	2020	0.423	0.010	0.7	4.8	7.7	0.0	0.90	1.00	0.94	H
BG3MA00324MS1239	Garvanovo Reservoir	L13	2020	1.105	0.042	12.4	36.8	4.9	4.2	0.37	0.47	0.40	M
BG3TU05239MS0040	Malko Sharkovo Reservoir	L13	2020	0.393	0.013	0.7	3.2	8.3	0.2	1.00	1.00	1.00	H
BG3MA00347MS0280	Mechka Reservoir	L13	2020	0.210	0.010	1.4	10.1	5.8	0.4	0.70	0.84	0.74	G
BG4ST0000NMS001	Stoikovtsi Reservoir	L13	2020	0.380	0.010	1.2	13.8	6.6	0.1	0.63	1.00	0.76	G
BG3MA03929MS0371	Sushitsa Reservoir	L13	2020	0.270	0.010	1.7	3.3	6.2	0.1	1.00	1.00	1.00	H
BG3MA04629MS0451	Svezhen Reservoir	L13	2020	0.638	0.010	5.6	11.4	6.0	0.1	0.67	0.95	0.76	G
BG3MA18739MS0071	Trakiets Reservoir	L13	2020	0.540	0.041	6.5	14.9	5.0	1.1	0.62	0.47	0.57	M
BG3MA00631MS0720	Vacha Reservoir	L13	2020	0.100	0.010	1.8	4.2	6.2	0.0	0.95	1.00	0.97	H
BG1YN43199MS021	Al. Stamboliyski Reservoir	L14	2020			4.7	4.0	6.5	0.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	H
BG1VT00325MS031	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir	L14	2020	0.785	0.010	0.8	2.3	5.6	0.0	1.00	0.89	0.96	H
BG1L14VTHM002_EEA	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir - tail	L14	2020	0.583	0.018	1.2	6.4	6.6	0.0	0.90	1.00	0.94	H
BG1OG00739MS031	Ogosta Reservoir	L14	2020			4.6	4.3	4.8	0.0	1.00	0.50	0.83	H
BG1L14OGHM004_EEA	Ogosta Reservoir - tail	L14	2020	0.325	0.010	2.1	7.3	3.7	0.2	0.86	0.18	0.64	G
BG3AR00133MS0020	Ivaylovgrad Reservoir - wall	L15	2020			4.0	2.8	5.5	0.0	1.00	0.84	0.95	H
BG3MA00225MS0120	Ovcharitsa Reservoir	L15	2020			4.0	8.9	5.3	0.3	0.82	0.72	0.78	G

MonitoringSiteCode	SiteName	Type	Year	TN mg/L	TP mg/L	BV mm ³ /L	Chl µg/L	Q	Cyan mm ³ /L	nEQR Chl	nEQR Q	HLPI	ES
BG3MA02191MS0116	Rozov Kladenets Reservoir	L15	2020	2.888	0.682	21.1	90.8	1.9	18.7	0.19	0.09	0.16	B
BG2SE08331MS028	Aheloy Reservoir	L16	2020			22.9	27.4	5.1	0.7	0.55	0.69	0.60	M
BG2KA00233MS037	Eleshnitsa Reservoir	L16	2020	0.350	0.017	5.3	11.4	5.2	0.2	0.78	0.74	0.76	G
BG2KA08471MS261	Fisek Reservoir	L16	2020	0.745	0.046	12.5	34.7	5.3	2.1	0.48	0.80	0.58	M
BG1WO00814MS071	Rasovo Reservoir	L16	2020	1.518	0.076	45.3	88.6	5.5	7.4	0.22	0.89	0.44	M
BG2SE98935MS263	Troyanovo Reservoir	L16	2020	2.955	0.223	59.7	95.4	5.6	4.3	0.20	0.92	0.44	M
BG3MA03143MS1226	Byalo Pole Reservoir	L17	2020	2.698	0.127	40.8	121.1	4.7	12.2	0.16	0.49	0.27	P
BG3MA00338MS7269	Chirpan Reservoir	L17	2020	2.528	0.664	32.8	154.2	4.9	2.6	0.12	0.60	0.28	P
BG3MA03742MS0322	General Nikolaevo Reservoir-1	L17	2020	0.945	0.018	15.7	70.1	2.5	10.5	0.27	0.12	0.22	P

Poly- and hyperhaline transitional waters (L9, L10)

MonitoringSiteCode	SiteName	Type	Year	TN mg/L	TP mg/L	BV mm ³ /L	Chl µg/L arithm.mean	Chl µg/L geom.mean	Cyan mm ³ /L	nEQR MPI	ES
BG2PR01931MS011	Beloslavsko Lake - west	L09	2020	2.448	0.146	13.9	37.2	22.1	0.0	0.63	G
BG2PR00155MS012	Channel betw.Beloslavsko and Varna Lake (Channel 2)	L09	2020	1.155	0.106	9.5	38.7	29.3	0.0	0.67	G
BG2MA00019MS009	lake Mandra - east	L09	2020	0.653	0.169	2.1	65.8	52.1	0.2	0.39	P
BG2MA000611MS008	lake Mandra -west	L09	2020	0.873	0.264	2.5	61.5	53.5	0.0	0.43	M
BG2PR00155MS018	New Channel (Channel 1)	L09	2020	0.390	0.068	2.8	12.5	6.4	0.0	0.91	H
BG2PR00155MS016	Varna Lake - East	L09	2020	0.548	0.090	2.7	28.5	12.7	0.0	0.44	M
BG2PR00155MS013	Varna Lake - west	L09	2020	0.533	0.112	9.2	38.0	25.0	0.1	0.59	M
BG2SE90000MS021	Lake Atanasovsko - north	L10	2020	0.918	0.551	2.8	76.3	30.2	0.1	0.38	P
BG2L10SETR004_EEA	Lake Atanasovsko - south	L10	2020	0.518	0.034	3.2	35.7	18.5	0.0	0.43	M
BG2SE90000MS020	Lake Pomorie - south	L10	2020	0.765	0.047	2.3	9.9	6.0	0.3	0.89	H
BG2L10SETR003_EEA	Lake Pomorie - west	L10	2020	1.210	0.158	3.5	131.6	105.5	0.1	0.22	P

Transitional rivers (R16)

MonitoringSiteCode	SiteName	Type	Year	TN mg/L	TP mg/L	BV mm ³ /L	Chl µg/L arithm.mean	Chl µg/L geom.mean	nEQR MPI	ES
BG2RE92529MS496	Butamiyata River- estuary	R16	2020	0.510	0.030	0.9	9.0	6.7	0.79	G
BG2SE00219MS228	Fandakliyska River - estuary	R16	2020	3.133	0.777	15.2	83.2	60.2	0.41	M
BG2IU6915MS002	Karaagach River - estuary	R16	2020	1.685	0.407	3.6	26.1	24.7	0.64	G
BG2IU00081MS254	Lisovo Dere River (Izgrevsko Dere) - estuary, Tsarevo	R16	2020	0.380	0.063	1.4	9.6	7.7	0.56	M
BG2IU07211MS404	Ropotamo River - before estuary, bridge on E 87	R16	2020	0.600	0.185	1.6	6.3	5.1	0.61	G
BG2IU200R005RP14	Ropotamo River in MR "Veliov Vir"	R16	2020	1.393	0.086	3.2	16.9	14.5	0.36	P
BG2RE00219MS497	Silistar River - before inflow into Black Sea (estuary)	R16	2020	0.548	0.013	2.5	7.5	6.7	0.64	G
BG2VE111MS001	Veleka River – Sinemorets village	R16	2020	0.475	0.052	0.5	3.3	2.6	0.77	G

